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Emerging Nanomaterials for Per- and Polyfluorinated Substances

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Detection

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Abstract

Per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are manmade chemicals that have been extensively used in a wide range of industrial and consumer applications due to their extraordinary features. PFAS has caused potential risks because of their persistence and bioaccumulation, consequently causing possible harm to human health and ecosystems. The fabrication of novel sensing technologies is an attractive approach that can address the limitations of conventional chromatographic techniques. This review highlights cutting-edge improvements in PFAS nano-sensor engineering, emphasizing molecular chemistry advancements in optical, electrochemical, aptamer-based, and immune-based nanosensors. Insights into tried-and-tested tactics by receiving an in-depth examination of each nano-sensor's detecting approach at the molecular level are elucidated. Potential mechanisms of interaction between PFAS and emerging nanomaterials are presented, encompassing fluorophilic interactions, electrostatic interactions, ion-bridging interactions with divalent cations, hydrophobic interactions, π - π bonds, hydrogen bonds, ionic exchange, and Van der

31 Waals forces in conjunction with materials such as single-atom supported nanomaterials,
32 carbon dots, graphene, and metallic nanostructures. The review uses an integrated approach to
33 explore current difficulties and potential in PFAS nano-sensor manufacture. Notably, it
34 describes critical sensor development objectives and the challenges experienced during the
35 process. This comprehensive analysis aims to offer a complete viewpoint that may direct future
36 research toward a well-informed and strategic emphasis on enhancing PFAS detection
37 technology. Researchers and practitioners may gain greatly from the synthesized knowledge,
38 which makes it easier to create innovative and effective PFAS-detecting systems.

39 **Keywords:** PFOS, PFOA, Nano-sensors, Molecular Imprinted Polymers, Aptamers-based
40 Sensing, Immunosensors

41 1. Introduction

42 A large class of over 15,000 synthetic compounds known as per- and poly-fluoroalkyl
43 substances (PFAS) are recognized by strong carbon-fluorine linkages that give them
44 remarkable stability and resistance to degradation.¹⁻³ PFAS are widely used in consumer goods
45 and operations, making them widespread environmental pollutants.^{4,5} They are found in air,
46 water, soil, and even organisms due to their extensive usage in nonstick cookware, water-
47 resistant fabrics, firefighting foams, and industrial processes. Other sources are the chemical
48 and textile manufacturing units. Given that PFAS are resistant to natural degradation processes,
49 they have become prevalent in the ecosystem and pose long-term risks to humans.^{6,7} Over 5000
50 Chemical Abstracts Service (CAS) numbers are categorized as PFAS, and most have unknown
51 identities.⁸ Additionally, unknown precursors can break down and contribute to recognized
52 PFAS.

53 The increasing presence of PFAS in the environment is a rising alarm worldwide.^{9,10} PFAS
54 contaminate the environment through direct industrial discharges, runoff from landfills, and
55 wastewater treatment plant effluents, where they persist. Therefore, these substances have been
56 found in almost all environmental matrices, including water sources and aquatic ecosystems,
57 as well as remote regions unaffected by direct industrial activities.^{11,12} The contamination of
58 PFAS has been observed in urban and rural environments, highlighting the widespread impact
59 of these chemicals.^{13,14} A number of PFAS have the ability to concentrate and accumulate in
60 lower trophic level plants and animals, which are then ingested and bioaccumulated by higher
61 trophic level animals (i.e., top predators), heightening the challenge as their long-term
62 accumulation continues to raise ecological and health-related concerns over time.¹⁵ In a study

63 in West Virginia, USA, 45 distinct PFAS chemicals in various river otter tissues were taken
64 from several watersheds.¹⁶ The liver had the greatest median content of PFAS, followed by the
65 pancreas, lung, kidney, blood, brain, and muscle. The most common chemicals were
66 perfluoroalkyl sulfonates (PFASs), which made up 58–75% of the total concentrations, and
67 perfluoroalkyl carboxylates (PFACs), which made up 21–35%. Hexafluoropropylene oxide
68 dimer acid (HFPO-DA) was uncommon; however, some PFAS compounds, such as 8:2
69 fluorotelomer sulfonate (8:2 FTS) and 10:2 FTS, were often detected in the liver and bile.
70 Otters from different watersheds had lower liver amounts of PFAS than those gathered
71 downstream of a fluoropolymer manufacturing site. The study determined that the median
72 whole-body burden of PFAS was 1580 μg with blood levels of PFOS and PFOA above the
73 human toxicity reference values.

74 Based on probabilistic surveys, 98–99% of the population in the United States has measurable
75 amounts of at least one PFAS in their serum.¹⁷ Data analysis regarding PFAS concentrations
76 in municipal tap water in Massachusetts reveals a pattern of increasing contamination, with the
77 overall number of fluorinated compounds showing a notable rise of 5 to 320 times over 25
78 years.^{18,19} Moreover, a substantial percentage—up to 94%—of these substances are still
79 unknown (also known as undiscovered PFAS). The primary human exposure route, residential
80 drinking water, was first brought under investigation when perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) was
81 found in human blood samples (mean concentrations of 423 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$) among Americans who were
82 not exposed to these contaminants at work between 2002 and 2005.²⁰

83 PFAS poses a significant concern for both public health and environmental management.^{21,22}
84 Efforts to mitigate PFAS contamination require a comprehensive understanding of their
85 environmental occurrence, origins, and modes of transportation, which will inform effective
86 strategies for monitoring, remediation, and regulatory measures.^{23,24} It is crucial to consistently
87 monitor and identify PFAS contamination in air, water, and soil to assess the extent of
88 environmental pollution. Policymakers and regulatory agencies can then utilize this knowledge
89 to develop effective policies that minimize the impact on ecosystems. Additionally, given the
90 detrimental effects of PFAS on life, identifying sources of exposure is essential for protecting
91 public well-being.²⁵ Ongoing monitoring plays a vital role in creating efficient risk
92 management plans, legal requirements, and initiatives focused on public health. Detecting
93 PFAS is a fundamental aspect of informed decision-making aimed at safeguarding both human
94 health and the environment from potential risks associated with these persistent compounds.

95 A few review articles on PFAS sensors that offer a comprehensive summary of various other
96 methods of PFAS detection have been published in the preceding years.^{26,27} Unlike these
97 outstanding studies, we report on the latest developments in PFAS nano-sensor engineering
98 from a molecular chemistry standpoint. Nanoparticles play a pivotal role in sensing,
99 demonstrating significant progress in applications such as detecting and comprehending the
100 molecular structure of pollutants and addressing challenges in water treatment and pollution
101 prevention.^{28,29}

102 Sensor technologies for detecting PFAS have significantly progressed, with improvements in
103 sensitivity, efficiency, and precision in environmental monitoring being evident. More intricate
104 sensor platforms like novel molecular detection mechanisms that are nano-enabled and
105 nanoparticle-based sensors have replaced traditional detection methods.²⁷ These advancements
106 provide improved detection limits up to nanomolar concentrations and real-time monitoring
107 capabilities to expand the array of tools existing for PFAS sensing. Despite these progressions,
108 ongoing development is still necessary for PFAS detection sensor systems due to the challenges
109 posed by the diverse nature of PFAS chemicals and their complex matrices.³⁰ Continued
110 investigation and invention are required to overcome these limitations and promote the growth
111 of sensors with improved accuracy, specificity, and versatility. This effort is critical to meeting
112 the growing demand for reliable PFAS detection techniques and assuring their usefulness in
113 protecting the environment. Improving sensor technology can strengthen environmental
114 protection efforts and get closer to long-term solutions for efficiently addressing PFAS
115 pollution.

116 In the initial section, we have provided a concise overview of the physicochemical
117 characteristics of PFAS alongside their classification. We provide a succinct summary of the
118 nanomaterials-based approaches that are now available for PFAS detection along with their
119 drawbacks that arise in the course of developing new sensors, the objectives that must be
120 remembered, and lastly, the nano-sensors that have been created thus far. To let the reader
121 know how each sensor senses PFAS at the molecular level and to outline the previously tried
122 and tested things, we go into great depth about each sensor's detection method. After evaluating
123 the literature, a focused discussion session on potential mechanisms of PFAS interaction—
124 comprising fluorophilic interactions, electrostatic interactions, ion-bridging interactions with
125 divalent cations, hydrophobic interactions, π - π bonds, hydrogen bonds, ionic exchange, and
126 van der Waal forces—with emerging nanomaterials including carbon dots, graphene, and
127 metallic nanostructures has been conducted. We also systematically examined current

128 challenges and opportunities associated with the fabrication of PFAS nano-sensors, adopting
129 an integrative approach. This comprehensive analysis provides a holistic perspective, guiding
130 future research endeavors toward a more informed and strategic focus.

131

132 2. Physicochemical properties of PFAS

133 PFAS are fluorinated substances containing at least one fully fluorinated methyl ($-\text{CF}_3$), a
134 methylene carbon atom ($-\text{CF}_2-$), and fully fluorinated alkanediyl ($-\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n}-$) moieties or
135 aromatic rings. A few exceptions reported so far include the H/Cl/Br/I atom attached to any
136 carbon atom.³¹ With over 4700 PFAS varieties documented in the literature, the predominant
137 characteristic among these compounds is an alkyl chain with fluorine as a substituent (C-F
138 bond).^{32,33} This creates a whole plethora of divergent physical properties like high thermal
139 stability, enhanced chemical stability, strong acidity, and hydrophobic and lipophobic
140 surfactant properties. It is presumed that this difference in the properties of PFAS from its
141 hydrocarbon analogue is due to the incorporation of fluorine groups, and to understand its
142 properties first, we need to understand the properties of fluorine and C-F bond in particular.

143 Fluorine appears at $\chi = 4$ on Pauling's electronegativity scale the most by any elements present.
144 The atomic size is the smallest among the Period 2 elements, having an electronic configuration
145 of $1s^2, 2s^2, 2p^5$ as it experiences the high nuclear charge of nine protons. So, ionization by
146 removal of an electron to become F^+ is extremely endothermic ($-401.2 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) with the 2p
147 electrons held close to the nucleus. On the other hand, the fluorine atoms readily accept
148 electrons to attain a noble gas-like configuration with the most exothermic ($+78.3 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$)
149 among the Period 2 elements.³⁴ The high electronegativity of fluorine is compared to that of
150 carbon; thus, the C-F bond is the strongest among all the bonds reported in organic chemistry
151 ($105 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$), but in PFAS, bond dissociation energy (BDE) calculation reveals that it
152 requires higher BDE to dissociate the C-F in the $-\text{CF}_3$ moieties ($117.8\text{--}123.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) than the
153 C-F bonds in the $-\text{CF}_2-$ moieties ($106.4\text{--}113.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) (**Figure 1 A**).^{35,36} The C-F bond is
154 highly polarised due to the small size of fluorine, thus generating a partial charge over $\text{C}^{\delta+}$ and
155 $\text{F}^{\delta-}$ atoms. The resultant electrostatic attraction makes the bond less covalent and more
156 electrostatic (**Figure 1 B**). Particularly, the electrostatic interaction between the polarized $\text{C}^{\delta+}$
157 and $\text{F}^{\delta-}$ atoms further strengthens the bonds, putting them into persistent organic pollutants
158 (POPs).³⁷ This argument rationalizes the progressive shortening of the bond observed for

159 fluoromethane upon substitution by fluoro groups and is the shortest for tetrafluoromethane.
160 The polarization of the C-F bonds leads to a change in the H-C-H bond angle in the
161 hydrocarbon. The rationales come from the valence shell electron pair repulsion (VSEPR)
162 theory, which states the fluorine groups show an electron-withdrawing effect and pull the
163 valence electron towards itself, narrowing the F-C-H or F-C-F bonds.

164 The electron-electron repulsion of the electron-rich C-H bonds of PFAS increases, leading to
165 widening. On the contrary, the F groups are larger than the H groups, thus introducing steric
166 interaction to widen the F-C-F bond angle while narrowing the H-C-H bond angle, but this is
167 not the case. Thus, the H-C-H bond angle of methane is 109.5° which increases to 110.2° and
168 even widens for difluoromethane to become 113.8° .³⁸ Similar is the case for fluorosubstitute
169 hydrocarbons where despite the -ve charge density over the F atoms, the C-F bonds close up,
170 and the bond angles decrease with enhancement of repulsion between the electron-rich C-C
171 bonds, increasing the bond angle.³⁹ Apart from this comparison series of progressive
172 fluorinated methane, difluoromethane has the highest polarity over fluoromethane and trifluoro
173 methane. Thus, introducing CF₂-type functionalities in the molecules induces high polarity and
174 low viscosity. The van der Waals radius of Fluorine (1.47 Å), when compared to hydrogen
175 (1.20 Å), is large, resulting in steric congestion, and the substitution of all three fluorine atoms
176 dramatically changes the conformation of the PFAS molecule from its hydrocarbon analogue.
177 Steric repulsions are also observed between the fluorine atoms relative to 1,3 positions due to
178 the formation of a helical structure (**Figure 1 D**). With an increase in the van der Waals radius
179 from H to F, the C-C bond length of the carbon backbone gets stretched, and the C-C-C angle
180 gets twisted by 12° , forming a helical structure with right and left helices in equal proportion,
181 unlike the zig-zag conformation for hydrocarbons (**Figure 1 C**). Thus, PFAS are
182 conformationally rigid molecules having less conformational freedom, which is attributed to
183 different steric constraints imposed by the presence of F groups.

184 Apart from the tail part, they have a head group containing functionalities like carboxylates,
185 sulfonates, phosphates, amines, and many more (**Figure 1 A**). Owing to the strong electron-
186 withdrawing nature of the perfluoroalkyl chains, it enhances the acidity of the OH groups and
187 diminishes the basicity of the organic functionalities present in the head group.⁴⁰ The increase
188 of acidity is also an attribute of the hyperconjugative stabilization by the β -fluorination. So, the
189 pKa values drop when H atoms are replaced by F atoms in the alkyl chain. Despite the high
190 electronegativity and lone pair over F, the low s and p orbitals are low-lying and relatively less
191 polarizable, making them bad hydrogen bond acceptors. Thus, to study the sorption behaviour

192 of PFAS, the pH of the solution becomes a crucial factor because it contains ionizable
193 functional groups in protonated or deprotonated forms. Anionic character is shown by
194 functionalities like carboxylic acid, phosphoric acid, phosphonic acid, and sulfuric acid when
195 they release the H^+ ions in the solution. Cationic functionalities are due to the presence of
196 amines that can accept H^+ from the solution or the presence of quaternary ammonium
197 functionalities. The Zwitterionic PFAS consists of two or more of the above-mentioned
198 functionalities. Lastly, there are few reported alcoholic PFAS which does not ionize in an
199 aqueous solution, leading to the formation of non-ionic PFAS.⁴¹

200 PFAS are very weakly interacting via both intermolecular and intramolecular pathways owing
201 to the low polarizability of the F groups, which can be characterized by their high volatility and
202 low boiling compared to their hydrocarbon analog. The lipophobic character of PFAS
203 originates due to the lack of van der Waals forces. These characteristics of PFAS pose severe
204 challenges in selective sensing and remediation. The exceptionally low surface tension of
205 PFAS is an attribute of meager intermolecular forces between the interacting molecules.⁴²
206 Despite the high dipole moment of the CF_2 groups, PFAS shows lower critical micellar
207 concentration (CMC) (i.e., the threshold concentration of any PFAS molecule in solution above
208 which it spontaneously forms micellar aggregates) than their hydrocarbon counterpart, as the
209 dipole moments of the CH_2 groups cancel out each other in the helical chain structure, giving
210 rise to its non-polar and hydrophobic character.

211 PFAS are from a unique fluororous phase via the creation of a phase boundary when encountering
212 a mixture of polar and non-polar solvents; this highlights its amphiphilic character. Partitioning
213 of fluororous materials resembling a biphasic separation process is driven by the free energy of
214 intermolecular interaction of PFAS in the two phases.⁴³ This can be achieved by following two
215 steps. The first step is the formation of a superstructure, where energy consumption leads to
216 assembling the PFAS molecules, further minimizing the surface tension. This required free
217 energy depends on the interaction free energy of the PFAS molecules under self-assembly and
218 the assembly size. In the second step, once the self-assembly is established, they interact by
219 van der Waals forces or other interactions like H-bonding. This induces a change in physical
220 properties with a change in the concentration of the PFAS in the solution.

221

222 **Figure 1. A.** Representation of the structural properties of PFAS molecules having a
 223 fluorocarbon tail (depicted is the BDE of the C-F bond for $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups) and a
 224 functional head group. The head group may vary from molecule to molecule, with the main
 225 functionalities like carboxylate, phosphate, and sulfonate groups. **B.** structure and electron
 226 density map of hexachlorobenzene where the electron density is polarized towards the F groups
 227 having a reddish colour and the electron-deficient carbon backbone with blue colour. **C.**
 228 Illustrates different types of F-F steric repulsion interaction between geminal, vicinal, and 1,3
 229 substituted groups. **D.** Comparison of structural dissimilarities of PFAS with its hydrocarbon
 230 analogue where the hydrocarbon shows the carbon backbone in a Zig-zag structure, but due to
 231 enhanced steric repulsion in PFAS molecules, the carbon backbone attains a helical structure.

232 3. Classification of PFAS

233 PFAS can be classified based on their chain length, chemical structure, and functional groups
 234 attached to the carbon backbone. The detailed classification of PFAS is given below. **Figure 2**
 235 depicts the flowchart for categorizing PFAS based on carbon chain length, functional groups,
 236 and chemical structure.

237 3.1. Classification of PFAS based on carbon chain length

238 The categorization of PFAS according to carbon chain length is critical for understanding their
 239 environmental destiny, toxicity, and possible effects on human health and ecosystems.⁴⁴

240 Short-chain PFAS generally comprises perfluoroalkyl chains with fewer than six carbon atoms.
241 Short-chain PFAS include: Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS), perfluoropentanoic acid
242 (PFPeA), perfluorohexanoic acid (PFHxA), and perfluoroheptanoic acid (PFHpA). Long-chain
243 PFAS are composed of perfluoroalkyl chains containing six or more carbon atoms. Due to their
244 distinct features, such as oil and water repellency, thermal stability, and surfactant capabilities,
245 these compounds are widely employed in various industrial and consumer applications.^{1,21}
246 Long-chain PFAS include perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorooctanesulfonic acid
247 (PFOS), perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA), and perfluorodecanoic acid (PFDA). Concerns
248 regarding environmental persistence and bioaccumulation have led to the adopting of these
249 compounds as alternatives to long-chain PFAS.^{45,46} Short-chain PFAS are thought to have
250 lesser bioaccumulation potential and shorter environmental persistence than long-chain
251 PFAS.^{45,47,48} Long-chain PFAS are known to have higher bioaccumulation capacity and longer
252 environmental persistence than short-chain PFAS.^{45,47,48}

253

254 **3.2. Classification of PFAS based on chemical structure**

255 *3.2.1. Linear PFAS*

256 Linear PFAS have straight-chain perfluoroalkyl groups. The carbon atoms in these fluorinated
257 chains are arranged linearly. Linear PFAS may have distinct chemical and physical
258 characteristics depending on the length of their perfluoroalkyl chain. Linear PFAS include
259 perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS).

260 *3.2.2. Branched PFAS*

261 Perfluoroalkyl chains with branching points give branched PFAS its non-linear structures.
262 Their chemical and physical characteristics may be influenced by branching. Branched PFAS
263 may show different solubility, reactivity, and environmental destiny than their linear
264 counterparts. Certain perfluorocarboxylic and perfluorosulfonic acids are examples of
265 branched PFAS.

266 *3.2.3. Cyclic PFAS*

267 Perfluoroalkyl chains organized in rings or cycles make up cyclic perfluoroalkyl substances
268 (PFAS). The existence of ring structures in these compounds may give rise to unique
269 characteristics like enhanced stiffness or conformational flexibility. Compared to linear or

270 branching PFAS, cyclic PFAS may exhibit distinct environmental behaviors and toxicological
271 profiles. Perfluoropolyethers (PFPEs) and several perfluoroalkyl phosphonic acids are
272 examples of cyclic PFAS.

273 Chemical structure-based categorization of PFAS sheds light on the variety of these substances
274 as well as their possible characteristics and behaviors. It is essential to comprehend the
275 structural properties of perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) to forecast their destiny in the
276 environment, evaluate their toxicity, and create mitigation plans that work.

277 **3.3. Classification of PFAS based on functional groups**

278 *3.3.1. Perfluoroalkyl Sulfonates (PFASs)*

279 PFASs are composed of a perfluoroalkyl chain with an attached sulfonate ($-\text{SO}_3^-$) functional
280 group. These substances have excellent heat stability and potent surfactant qualities. PFASs
281 are often utilized in industrial settings as coatings, firefighting foams, and surfactants.
282 Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) and perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBAS) are two
283 examples of PFASs (PFBS).

284 *3.3.2. Perfluoroalkyl Carboxylates (PFCAs)*

285 A perfluoroalkyl chain is joined to a carboxylate ($-\text{COO}-$) functional group in PFCAs. Due to
286 their chemical stability and surfactant qualities, these compounds are widely employed in
287 various consumer and industrial applications. PFCAs are frequently discovered in the
288 environment as pollutants and show modest thermal stability. Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)
289 and perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA) are two examples of PFCAs (PFNA).

290 *3.3.3. Perfluoropolyethers (PFPEs)*

291 Ether linkages ($-\text{O}-$) in the perfluoroalkyl chain are present in PFPEs. These substances are
292 renowned for having strong chemical and thermal stability as well as outstanding lubricating
293 qualities. PFPEs are often utilized in a variety of industrial applications as hydraulic fluids,
294 lubricants, and heat transfer fluids. Grease and oils made of perfluoropolyether are examples
295 of PFPEs.

296 *3.3.4. Perfluoroalkyl Phosphonic Acids (PFPA)s*

297 A perfluoroalkyl chain is joined to a phosphonic acid ($-\text{PO}(\text{OH})_2$) functional group in PFPA.s.
298 These substances have strong solubility in polar liquids and work well as corrosion inhibitors.
299 Applications needing corrosion protection, such as surface treatment and metal plating, employ

300 PFPAs. Perfluorooctylphosphonic acid (PFOPA) and perfluorodecylphosphonic acid
301 (PFDoPA) are two common PFPAs.

302 3.3.5. Perfluoroalkyl Phosphinic Acids (PFPIAs)

303 A perfluoroalkyl chain is joined to a phosphinic acid (-PO(OH)) functional group in PFPIAs.
304 These substances are efficient metal ion sequestrants with potent chelating properties. PFPIAs
305 are used in chemical synthesis, wastewater treatment, and metal extraction, among other
306 sectors. Perfluorooctylphosphinic acid (PFOPiA) and perfluorodecylphosphinic acid
307 (PFDoPiA) are two examples of PFPIAs.

308 3.3.6. Perfluoroalkyl Phosphates (PFPs)

309 A perfluoroalkyl chain is joined to a phosphate (-PO₄) functional group in PFPs. Due to their
310 excellent flame resistance, these substances are utilized as flame retardants in textiles and
311 polymers. PFPs are also utilized in specialized applications like lubricants and hydraulic fluids.
312 Perfluorooctylphosphate (PFOP) and 2-(Perfluorohexyl) Ethanol Phosphate (PFHxP) are two
313 examples of PFPs.

314 Functional group-based PFAS categorization sheds light on the substances' chemical makeup,
315 uses, and environmental characteristics. To evaluate PFAS's environmental destiny, toxicity,
316 and possible threats to ecosystems and human health, it is essential to comprehend the various
317 functional groups that make up these substances.

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318 **Figure 2.** Classification of PFAS based on carbon chain length, functional groups, and
319 chemical structure with examples.

320

321 4. Traditional PFAS detection methods and their limitations

322 PFAS detection has been performed using chromatographic techniques such as Liquid
323 chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS), Liquid chromatography-mass
324 spectrometry/mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-
325 MS), ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC), and HPLC.⁴⁹ The LC-MS/MS
326 technique has long been established as the gold standard for PFAS detection due to its
327 remarkable sensitivity, accuracy, and reliability.

328 Methods 533, 537, and 537.1, certified by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), are
329 essential for identifying PFAS and providing standardized procedures for tracking these
330 enduring pollutants.^{50–52} Solid-phase extraction (SPE) utilizing a polystyrene-divinylbenzene
331 (SDVB) resin is used in Method 533. The LC-MS/MS, equipped with a C18 column, is then
332 utilized for analysis to provide enhanced column efficiency and analyte resolution in shorter
333 run times. This technique has been useful in measuring PFAS in various aqueous media,
334 including drinking water, with LOD between 1.4 to 16 parts per trillion (ppt) for twenty-five
335 analytes. The drawbacks of using this analytical method include the 35-min minimum LC-
336 MS/MS run time, and the sole focus on analyzing drinking water samples. The solid-phase

337 extraction methodology with LC-MS/MS investigation is shared by Method 537, an expansion
338 of Method 533 that enables the measurement of 29 PFAS. Although it effectively identifies
339 PFAS in drinking water, it is primarily designed for the given matrix and has the same time
340 constraint of 35 min as Method 533. Aiming to improve analytical procedures, Method 537.1
341 has been refined in response to these restrictions. Method 537.1 reports reduced detection limits
342 ranging from 0.71 to 2.8 ppt, with an emphasis on eighteen PFAS analytes. Its primary focus,
343 like those of its predecessors, is on drinking water analysis, which highlights the necessity for
344 wider application to a variety of matrices such as soil, food, and air.

345 Though the EPA has not recommended it, other research groups have presented multiple
346 modifications to these approaches. For instance, dispersive solid-phase extraction (d-SPE) was
347 used to assess the amounts of PFOA and PFOS in honey samples.⁵³ Up to 87% of the sample
348 was recovered and subjected to micro-ultrahigh performance liquid chromatography
349 (UHPLC)-MS/MS analysis. The d-SPE technique distinguishes itself from SPE cartridges,
350 which may face clogging issues when extracting a contaminated matrix. In contrast, the d-SPE
351 method employs a minimal quantity of sorbents dispersed in the aqueous solution. This
352 approach ensures efficient compound recovery and minimizes solvent usage while optimizing
353 the utilization of sorbent surface area.⁵⁴ Therefore, more research on d-SPE for PFAS analysis
354 in various water matrices should be conducted. Another quick and easy analytical technique
355 for analyzing perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCAs) in water medium at small concentrations.⁵⁵
356 This study used tetrabutylammonium (TBA) as an ion pair in combination with solid phase
357 micro extraction (SPME), followed by in-port derivatization–GC–negative ion chemical
358 ionization MS. This method recommended applying this approach for the quick screening of
359 PFCAs in ecological matrices since involved shorter analytical times, fewer volumes of sample
360 and solvent, and better recoveries.

361 To fully comprehend the fate and transit of fluorinated compounds, especially PFAS, in the
362 environment, it is imperative to close the fluorine mass balance.⁵⁶ Researchers may ascertain
363 the presence and distribution of PFAS in the environment by utilizing the conventional
364 analytical methods stated above and their modifications. **Figure 3** provides an outline of the
365 analytical techniques that may be applied to close the fluorine mass balance. The fluorine mass
366 balance can make us understand the mechanisms by which PFAS enter, migrate through, and
367 depart environmental compartments by considering all sources, sinks, and transformations of
368 these chemicals. This knowledge is essential for evaluating the possible concerns connected to
369 the presence of PFAS, such as its persistence, bioaccumulation, and possible negative impacts

370 on ecosystems and public health. Closing the fluorine mass balance also makes it possible to
 371 pinpoint information gaps and create more precise prediction models for the behavior of PFAS
 372 in the environment, which helps with the creation of efficient management plans to lessen their
 373 effects.

374

375 **Figure 3.** An outline of the analytical techniques that may be applied to close the fluorine mass
 376 balance in PFAS. The widths of the boxes show the general coverage of the technique within
 377 the appropriate category of fluorinated chemicals, and the heights indicate the general
 378 sensitivity of the method as it is generally used. Reproduced from Ref.⁵⁶. Copyright 2024 ACS.

379 Although the EPA-approved methods and their modifications have been instrumental in
380 detecting PFAS, their drawbacks—such as the time-consuming nature of analysis and matrix
381 specificity—highlight the need for more sophisticated sensor approaches. Also, the issue of
382 peak separation with PFOA and PFOS in chromatographic systems is one of the most well-
383 known drawbacks. This is because the blank comes from common polymeric materials, which
384 means that PFOA may be maintained and eluted after the injected PFOA.⁵⁷ Only volatile, semi-
385 volatile, and neutral PFAS can be detected by gas chromatography (GC) and requires
386 a combination of electron impact (EI) or chemical ionization (CI) to provide the benefit of mass
387 spectral library application, which limits its applicability and makes it less common than LC.⁸
388 Nevertheless, the LC-MS method has drawbacks comparable to those of the GC-MS technique,
389 including the need for lengthy sample analysis and high costs (average cost of \$400/sample
390 analysis) for typical environmental monitoring applications.⁵⁸ It is essential to have rapid,
391 portable, affordable, and easy-to-use detection techniques to fulfill the increasing need for
392 thorough PFAS monitoring in a range of environmental settings.

393 A promising strategy to circumvent the limitations of existing technologies is to use advanced
394 nano-sensors that use newly developed nanomaterials and sensing processes. This will ensure
395 that PFAS can be detected effectively and widely outside standard laboratory settings with
396 better LOD and improved precision.

397 **4. Nano-sensors for PFAS detection**

398 A wide range of nanomaterials with 0D, 1D, 2D, and 3D dimensions, both organic and
399 inorganic in origin, have unique physiochemical characteristics that can be used to make
400 sensors for detecting PFAS and other organic contaminants.^{59,60} These nanoparticles are vital
401 components that provide a diverse framework for customizing sensor performance.^{61,62} The
402 categorization of PFAS sensors is inextricably tied to the underlying processes with materials
403 and output signals (**Figure 4**). Optical sensors use nanomaterials with various optical
404 characteristics to modulate light signals in order to detect PFAS. Surface-enhanced Raman
405 scattering (SERS) sensors, made possible by nanomaterials, use increased Raman signals to
406 detect PFAS with more specificity. Electrochemical sensors, which use nanomaterials with
407 good electrocatalytic capabilities, provide quantitative signals indicative of PFAS
408 concentrations via electrochemical processes. Immunosensors are based on functionalized
409 nanomaterials, which allow for the selective binding of PFAS to antibodies on nanomaterial
410 surfaces, resulting in measurable signals. Microfluidics sensors incorporate nanoparticles into

411 microfluidic systems, providing accurate and regulated PFAS detection while also increasing
 412 overall efficiency and speed in sensing operations. This comprehensive viewpoint highlights
 413 the critical significance of nanomaterials in several sensor modalities for PFAS detection,
 414 stressing their subtle contributions to sensor design and operation.

415 **Figure 4.** Types of PFAS nano-sensors based on underlying processes with materials and
 416 output signals.

417

418 4.1. Optical PFAS nano-sensors

419 Optical nano-sensors are an innovative class of sensing devices that use the unique features of
 420 nanomaterials to detect and analyze a wide range of chemicals at the nanoscale. These sensors
 421 use optical principles to detect light-matter interactions very sensitively and selectively.⁶³
 422 Nanomaterials, including nanoparticles, quantum dots, and nanocomposites, are crucial in
 423 improving the optical characteristics of these sensors. Colorimetry, fluorescence, plasmonics,
 424 and surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) are all methods used by optical nano-
 425 sensors. A nanomaterial inclusion enables fine control over sensor parameters, allowing
 426 customized responses to specific analytes. In the context of PFAS detection, optical nano-
 427 sensors have benefits such as fast reaction times, high sensitivity, and real-time operation.
 428 Optical nano-sensors are a promising technology at the vanguard of advanced sensing
 429 platforms because of their adaptability in various applications, from complex medical
 430 diagnostics to environmental monitoring.

431 4.1.1. Colorimetric PFAS nano-sensors

432 Nanomaterials that change color when a target, such as a specific molecule or ion, is present
433 are commonly employed in colorimetric sensors. The analyte concentration is connected with
434 the change in hue to generate an easy and visible readout. A detailed examination of optical
435 sensors employing gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) designed for sensing anionic pollutants,
436 specifically considering PFOS and PFOA.⁶⁴ Various optical sensors were constructed,
437 employing AuNP as the experimental basis for anions. The identification process for the
438 targeted anions involves induced aggregation, binding of anions, release (of dye or other
439 substances), and etching of AuNP (**Figure 5. A**). The functionalization of AuNPs in these
440 sensors involved employing thiol-terminated polystyrene or monolayers of alkane thiolates
441 terminated with poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG-thiol) and perfluorinated thiols (F-thiol). In the
442 former configuration, PFOA dislocates the polystyrene ligands by attaching them to the
443 AuNPs, leading to aggregation through fluorine-fluorine (F-F) interactions. This aggregation
444 induces a discernible color shift from red to blue-purple. Notably, the observed color change
445 is perceptible to the naked eye, albeit with a detection threshold above 103 ppm, a
446 comparatively elevated concentration. The authors propose the potential for color-changing
447 aggregation induced by perfluorinated carboxylic acids (PFCAs) as a broader class. In the latter
448 sensor design, the F-thiol functionalization facilitates the binding of PFAS via F-F interactions,
449 ensuing in the precipitation of AuNPs from the solution. With increasing PFAS concentration,
450 the red color intensity of reaction media diminishes. This color modulation is observable and
451 quantifiable through visual inspection and spectroscopy. Due to the inherent affinity of PFAS
452 for the F-F interaction, the sensor can detect multiple PFAS species with different functional
453 moieties, although short-chain PFAS (<C7) display reduced sensitivity attributed to decreased
454 hydrophobicity. Remarkably, the sensor achieves a detection limit as low as 10 ppb for long-
455 chain PFAS (>C7).

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456 **Figure 5. A.** Illustration of possible Au NPs and target analyte interactions. Reproduced from
 457 Ref.⁶⁴. Copyright 2017 Elsevier. **B.** MoS₂/Fe₃O₄ nano-flowers for the colorimetric
 458 determination of PFAS can produce a blue hue when 3,3,5,5-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) is
 459 oxidized in H₂O₂. Reproduced from Ref.⁶⁵. Copyright 2019 Elsevier.

460

461 In another study, MoS₂/Fe₃O₄ nano-flowers have been employed as a platform for the
 462 colorimetric detection of PFAS due to its inherent peroxidase-mimicking and electroactive
 463 properties, which can produce a blue hue when 3,3,5,5-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) is oxidized
 464 with H₂O₂, as illustrated in **Figure 5. B.**⁶⁵ The recognition mechanism involves electrostatic
 465 interactions and hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl groups of the Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles
 466 and the sulfonate groups of PFOS. Additionally, the steric hindrance effect resulting from the
 467 spatial arrangement of these moieties contributes to the sensor's excellent specificity. To assess
 468 the sensors' specificity, various target chemicals, including analogs of PFOS such as octanoic
 469 acid (OA), decanoic acid (DA), dodecanoic acid (DDA), dodecandiol, 1-dodecyl amine,
 470 sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), sodium dodecyl benzene sulfonate (SDBS),
 471 cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), sodium octadecanesulfonate, and 1-hexadecane
 472 sulfonate (SHDS), were introduced as interferences during the detection. The recovery rate for
 473 these interfering substances in river and tap waters was found to be ~85%. This underlines the
 474 robustness and applicability of the MoS₂/Fe₃O₄ nano-flower-based sensor for PFAS detection

475 in complex environmental samples. **Table 1** represents the attributes of the reported optical
476 PFAS nano-sensors. View Article Online
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477 Colorimetric PFAS nano-sensors have benefits such as quick and visually perceptible
478 detection, making them a natural choice for on-site monitoring of PFAS. Detection levels may
479 vary depending on the specific PFAS compounds targeted and the sensor design but commonly
480 fall within the range of 1 to 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$. These sensors frequently have excellent sensitivity,
481 allowing them to detect tiny concentrations, and their simplicity allows for user-friendly
482 applications that do not require complicated equipment. However, the possibility for
483 interference from compounds with comparable color-changing capabilities limits the
484 specificity of colorimetric PFAS nano-sensors in complicated sample matrices. Furthermore,
485 they may impose detection thresholds because they rely on observable color changes, making
486 them less suited for ultra-trace PFAS levels. Furthermore, colorimetric sensors may lack the
487 quantitative precision of more complex analytical techniques, making it challenging to detect
488 PFAS concentrations correctly. Quantitatively, the precision of colorimetric sensors may vary,
489 with detection errors typically falling within the range of $\pm 10\%$ to $\pm 50\%$, depending on factors
490 such as sensor design, calibration, and environmental conditions.

491 **Table 1.** Attributes of various colorimetric PFAS nano-sensors reported.

Optical Sensor Types	Platform Nanomaterial	Receptor/Probe	Target analyte	Mechanism/ PFAS interaction	Range (µg/L)	LOD (µg/L)	Ref.
Colorimetry	Au NPs	PEG-thiols And PFAS terminated (Fthiols) alkanethiols modified Au NPs (Au@PEG-F NPs)	PFOA, PFOS, PFBS, PFH _x S, PFHpA, PFNA, PFT _r DA, PFT _e DA, PFH _x DA, PFODA	Color change and SPR peak shift in UV-visible spectra	10 ² –10 ⁴	100	⁶⁶
	Fe ₃ O ₄ NPs	3D magnetic MoS ₂ /Fe ₃ O ₄ nanoflowers	PFOS	Hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl groups of the Fe ₃ O ₄ NPs and the sulfonate groups of PFOS and steric hindrance causes electrostatic contact.	50.01 to 6251.58	4.3	⁶⁷
	Au NPs	Poly (styrene)- coated Au NPs	PFOA, tridecafluorohepta noic acid	F-F interactions are used to aggregate Au NPs.	1.04 × 10 ⁵ – 2.07 × 10 ⁵	104,000	⁶⁸
	Carbon dots (CDs)	-	PFOS	Ground-state complex formation between CDs	0.5–8	7.587 × 10 ⁻²	⁶⁹

	MOFs-derived Co-N-C nanosheets (CoNCN)	3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB)	PFOS	The oxidase-mimicking property of CoNCN due to $\bullet\text{OH}$, O^{2-} and ${}^1\text{O}^2$ oxidize TMP (oxTMB), and the addition of PFOS fade the blue color of oxTMB	0.01 to 100	0.02	⁷⁰
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492

493 **4.1.2. Fluorescence PFAS nano-sensors**View Article Online
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494 To detect PFAS, fluorescence-based PFAS nano-sensors use the concepts of "turn on" or "turn
 495 off" procedures. The presence of PFAS causes a considerable increase in fluorescence intensity
 496 in a "turn on" configuration, generally due to particular binding or interaction between PFAS
 497 and the nanomaterials or displacement of fluorophores, resulting in a perceptible and
 498 quantitative signal augmentation. In contrast, in a "turn off" mechanism, the fluorescence
 499 intensity decreases following PFAS engagement, often due to quenching effects or the complex
 500 formation, allowing for sensitive and selective PFAS detection with detection limits ranging
 501 from ng/L to $\mu\text{g/L}$ depending on the specific nanomaterial used, experimental conditions, and
 502 detection method employed, via deviations in the emission characteristics of fluorescent
 503 nanomaterials (**Figure 6. A.**). These technologies provide flexible approaches for constructing
 504 very sensitive and selective PFAS sensors based on fluorescence responses.

505
 506 **Figure 6. A.** Illustration representing the two possible mechanisms of fluorescence
 507 manipulations, either by releasing fluorophores or by forming a ternary complex of the
 508 fluorophore, receptor, and PFOs. Reproduced from Ref.⁷¹. Copyright 2023 Royal Society of
 509 Chemistry. **B.** The schematics of turn-off sensing of PFOS anions via energy and charge
 510 transfer channels by MIP-SiO₂ NPs. Reproduced from Ref.⁷². Copyright 2014 Elsevier. **C.** The
 511 schematics of the interaction between SeN-CDs and PFOA for fluorescence quenching turn off
 512 sensing. Reproduced from Ref.⁷³. Copyright 2019 Springer.

513
 514 Using a surface molecular imprinting approach, Feng and colleagues created a fluorescence
 515 sensor for perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS, C₈F₁₇SO₃).⁷² The molecularly imprinted
 516 polymer (MIP) was immobilized onto SiO₂ NPs throughout this procedure. A hybrid monolayer
 517 consisting of a covalently anchored fluorescent dye and organic amine was generated on the
 518 MIP-SiO₂ NPs surface under acidic conditions (pH 3.5), functioning as receptor sites for

519 C₈F₁₇SO₃ via acid-base pairing and hydrogen-bond interactions. The fluorescence quenching
520 was caused by electron transfer between the fluorescent dye and PFOS, which was enhanced
521 by PFOS selective binding within the polymer matrix's recognition cavities. Surface-anchored
522 primary amino ligands incorporated into SiO₂ NPs with molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP)
523 caps acted as recognition elements. These ligands engaged PFOS through robust acid-base
524 and/or hydrogen-bond interactions. Upon rebinding to the recognition cavities, PFOS anions
525 caused the fluorescence emission of the dye FITC to quench, employing energy and charge
526 transfer pathways (**Figure 6. B**). The effectiveness of this quenching process correlated with
527 PFOS's binding affinity to the surface of MIP-capped NPs. The proposed method demonstrated
528 precise and selective detection of PFOS in water, achieving a detection limit as low as 5.57
529 μg L⁻¹. The linear relationship extended across a concentration range of 5.57-48.54 μg L⁻¹
530 (corresponding to 10.36-90.2 nM).

531 Carbon dots (CDs) are widely explored fluorescent nanomaterials in the ratio-fluoro-metric
532 sensing of organic and inorganic analytes.⁷⁴ A proposed fluorometric approach for PFOA
533 detection employing CDs co-doped with selenium and nitrogen (SeN-CDs) as a fluorescent
534 platform—a complex formation between SeN-CDs and PFOA showed rational quenching (turn
535 off).⁷³ With a LOD of 1.8 M, the method is suitable for quantitative aqueous sensing of PFOA
536 in the 10-70 M range. The combination of SeN-CDs and PFOA is shown in **Figure 6. C**.
537 Because carboxylate and fluorocarbon groups are hydrophilic and hydrophobic, respectively,
538 PFOA molecules tend to adsorb onto hydrophilic surfaces and interact with nearby surface
539 carboxylate groups via complexation. “Selenium has an electron affinity to receive electrons
540 because of its comparatively high electronegativity value, whereas fluorine in PFOA has an
541 even greater electronegativity to draw electrons from surrounding groups. As SeN-CDs are
542 extremely soluble, PFOA molecules can spontaneously reach the surface of the nanoprobe
543 and form complexes via carboxylate groups based on hydrophilic attraction. Additionally,
544 surface Se-containing groups are attracted to donate electrons to PFOA.”⁷³ This results in the
545 SeN-CDs-PFOA complex formation. Thus, the internal electron transfer of the chelation
546 complex accounts for the observed quenching and shorter longevity.

547 In another investigation, a fluorescent turn-on visual sensing of PFOS utilizing blue fluorescent
548 CDs and berberine chloride hydrate (BH) has been proposed.⁷⁵ It was observed that when BH
549 was introduced at pH 6.09 Britton-Robinson (BR) buffer solution, the fluorescence of CDs
550 decreased. No other perfluorinated molecule caused the fluorescence to be partially restored
551 (turned on) at 448 nm and seemed to have risen at 533 nm when PFOS was introduced.

552 PFOS/PFOA does not impair CDs. However, PFOS boosts the fluorescence intensity of BH.
553 This shows that fluorescence amplification in the CDs-BH system occurs due to an interaction
554 between BH and PFOS when PFOS is present. On the other hand, the CDs-BH-PFOS solution
555 has a more significant visualization impact (higher identification by the naked-eye) than the
556 BH-PFOS system (colorless to yellowish green). **Table 2** represents the attributes of the
557 reported fluorescence PFAS sensors.

558 Fluorescence-based PFAS nano-sensors have several benefits, including excellent sensitivity
559 with detection specificity often exceeding 90% for targeted PFAS compounds, enabling the
560 detection of trace amounts of PFAS with great accuracy. These sensors frequently give real-
561 time and quantitative results, allowing PFAS detection across a wide dynamic range. However,
562 drawbacks include the possibility of interference from complicated sample matrices, which
563 may impair sensor specificity, and the need for specialized equipment, which can raise the total
564 cost and complexity of the detection system. For example, different organic and inorganic
565 chemicals may interfere with the fluorescence signal in complex environmental samples such
566 as wastewater or soil extracts, resulting in false-positive or false-negative findings.
567 Furthermore, the photobleaching of fluorophores and sensitivity to environmental conditions
568 may cause difficulties in maintaining sensor stability over long periods.

569 **4.1.3. Optical scattering PFAS nano-sensors**

570 PFAS nano-sensors, based on optical scattering, use several methods, such as Raman
571 scattering, Rayleigh light scattering, resonance light scattering, and resonance shift, to provide
572 sensitive PFAS detection and quantification. For instance, Rayleigh light scattering methods
573 may identify PFAS compounds at concentrations as low as 0.1 ng/L, whereas Raman scattering
574 techniques can detect them as low as 1 ng/L. Even higher sensitivity is possible using resonance
575 shift and resonance light scattering methods, which have detection limits as low as 0.01 ng/L
576 for certain PFAS species. When incoming photons interact with PFAS molecules in Raman
577 scattering, specific frequency changes in the scattered light correlate to rotational and
578 vibrational transitions in the molecules.⁷⁶ PFAS nano-sensors monitor these optical scattering
579 events to identify molecular interactions, enabling accurate and targeted PFAS sensing in
580 diverse complex matrices. When the wavelengths of Rayleigh scattering and molecule
581 absorption coincide, a particular type of light scattering known as resonance light scattering
582 (RLS) occurs. This resonance, which is seen when incoming light interacts with specific
583 molecules, strengthens the scattering signal. Rayleigh light scattering and resonance shift-

584 based PFAS nano-sensors are not yet known. There isn't much evidence of advancements using
585 these particular sensing approaches in the research landscape in this field. There are, however,
586 few reports of PFAS nano-sensors using SERS, suggesting some advancement in substitute
587 sensing techniques.

588 The PFAS, metal surface distance, particle orientation, and conformation affect SERS and
589 metallic nanoparticle's (MNP) shape, size, and assembly. The intensity of the interaction
590 among the PFAS and MNP determines the signal enhancement. As seen in **Figure 7. A**, the
591 Raman intensity changes with the analyte's location. The position of the analyte determines the
592 Raman intensity: at position 1, there is minimal Raman scattering due to negligible
593 electromagnetic charge transfer external to the metal surface; at position 2, charge transfer with
594 MNP results in a weak Raman spectrum; and at position 3, significant electromagnetic charge
595 transfer causes enhanced Raman scattering, which is known as a hotspot and is attributed to
596 localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) effects.

597 Fang and colleagues used SERS methods to identify firefighting foams, essential sources of
598 PFAS in the environment.⁷⁷ They obtained LODs of 50 ppb for perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA)
599 by using two SERS substrates, namely nanosphere lithography Ag and graphene oxide (GO)
600 membrane, loaded with dye-fluoro surfactant (FS) precipitate ion pairs. The adsorption of
601 certain PFAS compounds was aided by adding Si-Ag-GO membranes with flat surfaces.
602 Experiments under controlled conditions showed that adding a dye, such as ethyl violet,
603 considerably enhanced the loading capacity of FS onto the GO surface. Using various colors,
604 the replacement of perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) with PFOA and modifications to the
605 ion-pair components were investigated, offering insights into the SERS substrates' detection
606 capabilities. The dye-FS-Ag and dye-FS-GO LOD assemblies were shown; the latter could
607 have a 50 ppb LOD. The silicon peak at 512 cm^{-1} is used as a reference for using a GO
608 membrane. The Raman spectrum analysis of the dye-FS-GO and dye-FS-GO LOD incubation
609 assemblies is displayed in **Figure 7. B-I**. **Table 2** represents the attributes of the reported
610 optical scattering PFAS sensors.

611 One of SERS's advantages is its adjustable surface, allowing for improved detection using
612 direct and indirect methods.⁷⁸ Furthermore, the technology's adaptability enables the creation
613 of nano-sensors with various uses. Nevertheless, there are obstacles to overcome, such as the
614 difficulty of fabricating the substrate, the possibility of signal fluctuation due to external
615 factors, and the related expense of creating highly reproducible SERS substrates. These issues

616 must be resolved for SERS-based PFAS nano-sensors to be widely used in practical
 617 applications.

618 **Figure 7.** A. Schematic of Surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) sensing for an organic
 619 analyte on AuNPs. Reproduced from Ref.⁷⁹. Copyright 2015 Royal Society of Chemistry. **B-I.**
 620 Shows that the Raman spectral analysis of the assemblage of dye-FS-GO; LOD of the
 621 assemblies of dye-FS-Ag (**J** and **K**) and dye-FS-GO (**H** and **I**). Reproduced from Ref.⁷⁷.
 622 Copyright 2016 Royal Society of Chemistry.

623 **Table 2.** Attributes of various fluorescence and optical scattering PFAS nano-sensors reported.
 624

Optical Sensor Types	Platform Nanomaterial	Receptor/Probe	Target analyte	Mechanism/ PFAS interaction	Range (µg/L)	LOD (µg/L)	Ref.
Fluorescence	SiO ₂ NPs	FITC dye- NH ₂ -APTS MIP	PFOS	Direct fluorescent recognition	5.57–48.54	5.57	⁷²
	Carbon dots (CDs)	Berberine chloride hydrate (BH)	PFOS	In BR buffer solution BH quench (Turn off) fluorescence of CDs and PFOS restored fluorescence (Turn on)	110.028–25006.3	10.853	⁷⁵
	Magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles	Guanidinocalix [5]arenes	PFOS, PFOA	Molecular van der Waals forces between electron-deficient GC5A-6C and the e-rich sulfonate head group of PFOS, as well as hydrogen bonding between Guanidium groups of GC5A-6C and the PFOS head group, lead to fluorescence enhancement (Turn on)	50–4000 (PFOS); 100-1000 (PFOA)	11.3 ± 0.2 (PFOS); 10.9 ± 0.1 (PFOA)	⁸⁰
	N-doped Carbon dots (N-CDs)	Ethidium bromide	PFOS	Through electrostatic interaction and hydrogen bonding, N-CDs can react with negatively charged PFOS, causing aggregation and fluorescence quenching (Turn off) and an increase in SOS, a scattering light signal.	0–1000.25	13.9	⁸¹

Chitosan doped CDs	Epichlorohydrin	PFOS	The sulfonate group of PFOS can complex with the amino group via hydrogen bonding or electrostatic reactions, enhancing the conjugation degree of H ₂ N-passivated CQDs and leading to enhanced fluorescence emission (Turn On)	$2 \times 10^{-5} - 2 \times 10^{-4}$	4×10^{-7}	82
CDs	-	PFOS, PFOA	Electron transfer mechanism and fluorescence quenching (Turn off)	$3 \times 10^{-3} - 16$ (PFOS); $0.05 - 1$ (PFOA)	5×10^{-3} (PFOS); 1×10^{-2} (PFOA)	83
CDs	-	PFOS	CDs-PFOS ground-state complex formation leading to static quenching (Turn off)	0.2–12	1.827×10^{-2}	69
NaYF ₄ UCNPs	Perfluorooctyltriethoxysilane functionalized tricolor probes	PFOS, PFOA, PFDA, PFNA, PFHpA, PFHxA, PFHxS	Hydrogen bonding between probes and PFOS, fluorescence quenching (Turn off) due to charge/energy transfer between the SiO ₂ layer and PFOS	-	20.005	84
QDs	Chitosan MIP	PFOS	Fluorescence quench (Turn on)	$20 \times 10^{-6} - 200 \times 10^{-6}$	60×10^{-6} (Serum); 85×10^{-6} (Urine)	82
Covalent organic frameworks	Lanthanide-doped nanocrystals	PFOS	Through hydrogen bonds or electrostatic interactions, the PFOS sulfonate groups interact with the amino groups and hydrogens on the	$90.02 \times 10^{-6} - 9$	75.02×10^{-6}	85

				benzene ring of the COFs and quench fluorescence (Turn on).			
	CdS quantum dots	3-mercaptopropionic acid (MPA)	PFOA	Aggregation-dispersion of MPA-CdS-QDs result in fluorescence Quenching (Turn off)	200–16000	120	⁸⁶
Optical Scattering	AgNPs on silicon	Dye-ethyl violet or methyl blue and graphene oxide coating	PFOA	Surface-enhanced Raman scattering	50–500	50	⁷⁷
	CDs	-	PFOS	Resonance light scattering	0.5–12	1.2045	⁶⁹

625

626 4.1.4. Plasmonic PFAS nano-sensors

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627 Plasmonic serves a significant part in the development of PFAS nano-sensors. AuNPs and
628 AgNPs are often used in PFAS detection plasmonic nano-sensors.⁸⁷ These nano-sensors use
629 the distinctive optical features of AgNPs and AuNPs, such as surface plasmon resonance
630 (SPR). SPR is an aspect of sensing that uses variations in refractive index close to a metal
631 surface. Surface plasmons are excited when polarized light strikes a metal surface at a particular
632 angle, causing the phenomena. SPR is used to detect PFAS and other pollutants in various
633 sensor platforms, such as optical fibers and nanoparticles.⁵⁸ In recent advancements, utilizing
634 SPR in conjunction with nanostructures and molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) has
635 improved sensitivity and selectivity, with detection limits for a variety of target analytes as low
636 as pg/mL.⁸⁸

637 MIP was deposited on a D-shaped plastic optical fiber (POF) shielded with a photoresist buffer
638 layer and a thin Au film.⁸⁹ To generate this optical platform, the POF cladding is removed
639 (along a half circle), the buffer layer is spin-coated over the uncovered core, and then the Au
640 film is sputtered. The multilayer on D-shaped POF contains a 60 nm thin Au film and a buffer
641 layer that is 1.5 μm thick. The POF has a 980 μm core (polymethyl methacrylate) and 10 μm
642 cladding (fluorinated polymer) in size. The SPR-POF sensor, a spectrometer (350 nm to 1023
643 nm), and a halogen lamp (360 nm to 1700 nm) coupled to a PC form the basis of this
644 straightforward and inexpensive experimental setup (**Figure 8**). The process entails building a
645 unique MIP with binding sites engineered to identify perfluorinated chemicals (PFCs)
646 precisely. A plasmonic POF, a kind of optical fiber intended to facilitate SPR processes, is
647 combined with this MIP. The refractive index at the POF surface varies due to MIP's interaction
648 with PFCs. The plasmonic POF's exceptional capacity to facilitate SPR makes the plasmonic
649 component so important. The local refractive index near the point of foci changes as PFCs bind
650 to the MIP, which causes noticeable changes in the SPR signal. PFCs may be directly and label-
651 free detected in water samples thanks to our real-time SPR change monitoring technique.

652 SPR's label-free detection and real-time monitoring capabilities make it an advantageous tool
653 for PFAS detection. Nevertheless, there are obstacles to overcome, such as the requirement for
654 specialized tools and possible interference from intricate sample matrices. SPR-based
655 biosensors for PFAS detection are being actively investigated by researchers, which is
656 advancing environmental monitoring. **Table 3** presents a comparative summary of the salient

657 features of each type of optical PFAS nano-sensor, emphasizing their real-time monitoring
 658 capabilities, sensitivity, specificity, detection principles, benefits, and drawbacks.

659 **Figure 8.** experimental setup and production techniques for implementing an SPR sensor in a
 660 D-shaped POF with an MIP receptor. Reproduced from Ref.⁸⁹. Copyright 2018 MDBI.

661 **Table 3.** The comparison of various optical PFAS nano-sensors.

Optical PFAS nano-sensor types	Detection Principle	Sensitivity	Specificity	Real-time Monitoring	Advantages	Disadvantages
Colorimetry	Color change in the presence of PFAS	Moderate	Limited	No (Visual Inspection)	Simple visual detection	Limited sensitivity
					No need for complex instrumentation	Quantification may be challenging
						Rapid response time
Fluorescence	Fluorescence Quenching or Enhancement in the Presence of PFAS	High	High	Yes	High sensitivity	Susceptible to background fluorescence
					Quantitative analysis capability	Photobleaching may occur
					Real-time monitoring	Signal interference from the sample matrix
Optical Scattering	Enhancement of Raman Signals in the Presence of PFAS	High	Molecular Specificity	Yes	High sensitivity	Signal reproducibility challenges
					Multiplexing capability	Complex fabrication processes
					Molecular specificity	
Plasmonic	Change in SPR Signals upon Binding of PFAS	High	High	Yes	Label-free sensing	Equipment complexity and cost
					Instantaneous monitoring	Limited to thin sensing layers on the sensor surface
					Highly sensitive	

662

663 4.2. Electrochemical PFAS nano-sensors

664 By applying the principles of electrochemistry to transform the binding events between PFAS
665 molecules and sensing surfaces into detectable electrical signals, electrochemical nano-sensors
666 present a viable approach to PFAS detection.^{90–92} The electrochemical sensor works based on
667 electrical current generated by oxidation-reduction reactions on electrode surfaces.^{93,94} To be
668 more precise, a conductive electrode surface is grafted with a selective chemical receptor,
669 which is usually nanosized for improved sensitization and interacts with a target analyte.⁹⁵ This
670 is the standard construction of an electrochemical sensor. A reference electrode, a counter
671 electrode, and a functional anode or cathode electrode are the three electrode types often
672 utilized in the system. The presence and quantity of the analyte are ascertained by comparing
673 the variation in electric current across the electrode caused by the analyte molecule attaching
674 to the receptor to calibration curves.

675 This technique often uses different electrode materials and surface changes to improve
676 sensitivity and selectivity. As a result, it offers a reliable and effective way to monitor PFAS
677 contamination in various environmental matrices.⁹⁶ There are many different types of
678 electrochemical sensors, and they are divided into different categories based on how strong an
679 electrical signal they can detect. For instance, conductometric sensors measure changes in
680 conductance (G), impedimetric sensors measure variations in impedance (Z) over frequency
681 (Hz) ranges, potentiometric sensors quantify variations in the ion-selective membrane potential
682 (mV), and voltammetric sensors quantify the variation in current (pA) that results from the
683 initial electrochemical reaction triggered by an applied voltage (mV). The two kinds of PFAS
684 electrochemical sensors that are most often described are voltammetric and potentiometric.
685 **Table 4** represents the attributes of the reported electrochemical PFAS sensors.

686 4.2.1. Voltammetric PFAS nano-sensors

687 Voltammetric PFAS nano-sensors can precisely detect and measure PFAS chemicals using the
688 electrical responses produced by voltammetric processes.⁹⁷ Enhancing sensitivity and enabling
689 real-time monitoring through integrating nanomaterials and advanced electrode modification
690 methods meet the pressing requirement for effective PFAS detection in various environmental
691 conditions such as pH fluctuation, salinity, and temperature. Pristine glassy carbon electrodes
692 (GCE) were modified using a drop-casting method to add an ultrathin coating of gold nanostars
693 (AuNS).⁹⁸ This modification aimed to increase the electrode's sensitivity to ferrocene
694 carboxylic acid, an electrochemical probe.⁹⁸ These AuNS-coated GCEs were then further

695 modified by adding a layer of *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*-PD) imprinted with
696 perfluorooctanesulfonate (PFOS) using cyclic voltammetry for electropolymerization. This
697 increased the sensor's sensitivity to PFOS, as seen in **Figure 9. A**. Differential Pulse
698 Voltammetry (DPV) was utilized to track the oxidation peak of ferrocene carboxylic acid
699 (FcCOOH) in its Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ states to examine the dynamics of the interaction between the
700 Molecular Imprinting Polymer (MIP) layer and PFOS. The oxidation peak for the
701 MIP/AuNS/GCE combination completely disappears in **Figure 9. A** before PFOS is removed,
702 demonstrating the MIP layer's capacity to prevent charge transfer between the working
703 electrode and the solution. This voltammetric sensor showed promise in PFOS detection, with
704 a 3 σ method-calculated exceptionally low LOD of 0.015 nM. The proposed sensing probe
705 demonstrated competence in identifying PFOS traces in tap water. Significant interferences
706 were found during the experiments, especially with perfluorobutanoic acid (PFBA) or
707 perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS). The smaller sizes of PFBA and PFBS molecules are
708 thought to be responsible for this interference phenomenon since they allow them to get
709 through the MIP layer and occupy PFOS-shaped voids through non-specific binding.
710 Therefore, it is essential to do a preliminary screening of unidentified samples to determine
711 whether smaller PFAS molecules, including PFBA and PFBS, are present.

712 Electropolymerized molecularly imprinted poly (*o*-phenylenediamine) (*o*-PD MIPs) with 170
713 \pm 10 nm (N=3) thickness in combination with ferrocene carboxylic acid (FcCOOH) as a
714 reversible redox probe was used to functionalize Au electrodes to counteract the low EC
715 activity of PFOS, which is evident in voltammograms (**Figure 9. B**).⁹⁹ A LOD of 0.02 μ g/L
716 was obtained using two linear working ranges of 0.05–2.45 and 4.75–750.19 μ g/L. This
717 produced a LOD more than 10 times more sensitive than the ambient PL for PFOS at 0.2 μ g/L.
718 The voltammetric signal drops when PFOS is present in the sample, establishing a correlation
719 between the signal and PFOS content. The relationship between the concentration of PFOS in
720 the solution and the voltammetric signal of the reporter molecule FcCOOH was shown to be
721 inversely proportional.

722 One of the most important benefits of using voltammetric PFAS nano-sensors is that they can
723 identify PFAS chemicals even at low concentrations, which makes it easier to respond quickly
724 to environmental contamination incidents⁹⁸. Additionally, adding nanomaterials improves
725 sensor performance by increasing PFAS detection sensitivity and selectivity as we discussed
726 above. Still, certain issues remain and require ongoing improvement. For nano-sensors to be
727 widely used and regularly monitored, the high expenses related to their creation and operation

728 must be addressed. Furthermore, improving electron transfer conditions and addressing non-
 729 specific binding problems—mainly when interacting compounds are present—will improve
 730 the precision and dependability of PFAS nano-sensors in complex environmental samples.
 731 Voltammetric PFAS nano-sensors can confirm their position as indispensable instruments in
 732 the continuous endeavors to observe and lessen the effects of PFAS pollution on the
 733 environment by addressing these areas for development.

734 **Figure 9.** A. Representation of the improved voltammetric sensor for PFOS using gold
 735 nanostars (AuNS) and molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP). Reproduced from Ref.⁹⁸.
 736 Copyright 2022 Elsevier. B. Schematic representation of functionalized Au electrodes using
 737 electropolymerized molecularly imprinted poly (o-phenylenediamine) (o-PD MIPs) in
 738 conjunction with ferrocene carboxylic acid (FcCOOH) as a reversible redox probe for
 739 voltammetric detection of PFOS. Reproduced from Ref.⁹⁹. Copyright 2018 American Chemical
 740 Society.

741

742 4.2.2. Potentiometric PFAS nano-sensors

743 Potentiometry, a method for measuring a system's voltage or electrical potential difference, is
 744 the foundation upon which potentiometric PFAS nano-sensors are based. These nano-sensors'
 745 excellent sensitivity and selectivity are particularly engineered to detect PFAS. The interaction

746 of PFAS compounds with the detecting components causes these nano-sensors to respond
747 potentiometrically, measured by electrical potential changes. This creative method uses
748 nanotechnology to improve PFAS detection accuracy, a breakthrough in environmental
749 sensing.¹⁰⁰

750 The electric potential drop by GenX PFAS binding to o-phenylenediamine (o-PD MIP) was
751 examined. This study observed a significant blockage of current flow.¹⁰¹ This strategy worked
752 well for hexafluoropropylene oxide-dimer acid (HFPO-DA), a GenX PFAS, with an LOD of
753 0.000083 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Interestingly, this LOD was higher than LC-MS/MS's sensitivity (0.0001
754 $\mu\text{g/L}$). The method involved coating a glassy carbon electrode with a 75 nm thick layer of o-
755 PD MIP using FcCOOH as a buffer (**Figure 10. A**). The inhibitory effect of the intercalation
756 of PFOS with the MIP, which was connected to the PFOS content in the sample, resulted in a
757 discernible loss of potential. Examining PFOS allowed the identification of concentrations as
758 low as 0.025 $\mu\text{g/L}$, demonstrating a 6.2% relative standard deviation. Notably, this sensitivity
759 is 250 times lower than that of the LC-MS/MS technique. The method remained significantly
760 more efficient, surpassing the respective PLs of 0.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for PFOS and 0.4 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for PFOA by
761 8 and 16 times, respectively.¹⁰²

762 A new method has been applied to improve the development and production of potentiometric
763 PFAS nano-sensors.¹⁰⁰ To accomplish potentiometric detection of PFOA, a MIP was
764 developed by electrodepositing polypyrrole (Py) of ~ 600 nm thickness onto a cheap electrode
765 surface, specifically pencil lead (**Figure 10. B**). To improve selectivity, methylene blue (MB)
766 by addition of the pyrrole polymer matrix. The purpose of this addition was to promote
767 selectivity by facilitating ion pair formation involving fluoro-surfactants, often found in MB
768 and aqueous film-forming foams (AFFFs). The nano-sensor established notable fluoro-
769 surfactant detection capabilities, including PFOA, PFOS, and 1H, 1H, 2H, and 2H-
770 perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (6:2FTS), at concentrations between 10 μM and 10 mM. The
771 PFOA LOD was notably reduced to around 100 nM, or 41 ppb, demonstrating the
772 potentiometric nano-sensor's sensitivity and usefulness in accurately and selectively
773 identifying PFAS chemicals.

774 Potentiometric PFAS nano-sensors are useful tools for analytical and environmental
775 applications because of their low detection limits and capacity for real-time monitoring. Certain
776 things still need to be worked on to increase their overall performance. Managing possible
777 influence from intricate sample matrices, maintaining long-term stability, and maximizing

778 scalability for broad use are among the difficulties. Potentiometric PFAS nano-sensors have
 779 great promise, and further research and development efforts should be directed toward
 780 addressing these obstacles to facilitate their broader application in regulatory compliance and
 781 environmental monitoring.

782 **Figure 10. A.** The figure caption describes the fabrication and functioning of μ -MIP:
 783 Molecularly Imprinted Polymer-Modified Microelectrodes for the Ultrasensitive
 784 Quantification of GenX (HFPO-DA) by potentiometry: (a) illustrates the oxidation of ferrocene
 785 methanol, producing a voltammogram; (b) demonstrates the electropolymerization of o-
 786 phenylenediamine, forming a molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) that traps GenX
 787 molecules. (c) The MIP layer insulates the electrode, affecting the current response during
 788 ferrocene methanol oxidation. (d) Extracting GenX exposes specific surface sites, influencing
 789 the current response, and in contaminated systems, GenX adsorption blocks surface sites
 790 correlating with analyte concentration. Reproduced from Ref.¹⁰¹. Copyright 2020 American
 791 Chemical Society. **B.** Schematic representation of the potentiometric response of the PFOA-
 792 MIP depends on the concentrations of various anions and the concentration of PFOA
 793 conditioning solution before the test. Reproduced from Ref.¹⁰⁰. Copyright 2016 Elsevier.

794

795 4.2.3. Photo-electrochemical PFAS nano-sensors

796 Novel photo-electrochemical sensors (PEC sensors) that work on photoelectric chemistry
 797 principles are emerging in the field of sensing technology.¹⁰³ These sensors are intended for
 798 the precise sensing of biological and chemical constituents. When exposed to light, the essential
 799 premise of PEC sensors is the creation of electric current via valence electron transfer inside
 800 the photoexcited material, which initiates chemical processes.¹⁰⁴ PEC sensors significantly

801 limit background noise by using light as an excitation source and photocurrents as recognition
802 signals, resulting in increased sensitivity compared to traditional technology.¹⁰⁵ This novel
803 technology takes advantage of light's distinctive characteristics and photo-induced currents,
804 establishing PEC sensors as viable instruments for improving the accuracy and sensitivity of
805 molecular research.

806 A nanostructured probe for PEC sensing that uses MIP-modified AgI nanoparticles-BiOI
807 nanoflake arrays as the photoactive electrode (designated as MIP@AgI-BiOINFs) was
808 constructed.¹⁰⁶ The MIP formation process is given in **Figure 11. A**. The AgI-BiOINFs were
809 produced in situ utilizing a simple sequential ionic layer adsorption and reaction (SILAR)
810 method, which also served as a matrix for grafting the MIP recognition element. This PEC
811 sensor detects PFOA with remarkable sensitivity and selectivity. When PFOA is absent,
812 triethanolamine (TEA) serves as an electron donor, amplifying the photocurrent on the
813 modified electrode MIP@AgI-BiOINFs/FTO (where FTO refers to fluorine-doped tin oxide
814 glass). Conversely, PFOA inhibits quencher molecules (TEA) from accessing the electrode
815 surface and capturing photo-generated holes, impeding this process (**Figure 11. B**).
816 Photocurrent gradually decreases until it ceases due to the steric barrier between AgI and PFOA
817 caused by PFOA adsorption on the MIP@AgI-BiOINF arrays. The PEC analysis exhibits
818 remarkable linearity throughout the 0.02 to 1000.0 ppb PFOA concentration range, with a LOD
819 of 0.01 ppb.

820 PEC sensors are inherently small, which makes it possible for them to be easily integrated into
821 handheld devices—an essential feature for monitoring.¹⁰³ Their facile integration across
822 various analytical domains, from environmental monitoring to biological diagnostics,
823 demonstrates their adaptability and promotes interdisciplinary applications. However, selecting
824 photoactive materials ideally is crucial to PEC sensor performance, which makes customizing
825 sensors for a given application difficult. Moreover, PEC sensors may be less accessible because
826 of the complexity of the instrumentation needed for their deployment. The considerable
827 expenses linked to developing and implementing PEC sensor technology may impede its wider
828 use. Despite these challenges, research is still being conducted to find solutions to these
829 constraints, opening the door for photo-electrochemical sensors to continue developing and
830 being used in various areas.^{107,108}

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834 **Figure 11. A.** Schematics of molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) formation **B.** Schematics
 835 of the SILAR deposition of AgI-BiOINFs films on MIP and the principle of PFOA PEC
 836 determination utilizing MIP@AgI-BiOINFs/FTO. Reproduced from Ref.¹⁰⁶. Copyright 2015
 837 Elsevier.

838

839 4.2.4. Impedance PFAS nano-sensors

840 Impedance PFAS nano-sensors operate based on the principle of electrical impedance,
 841 measuring the opposition that PFAS compounds pose to the flow of alternating current.⁹¹ These
 842 nano-sensors leverage the interaction between PFAS molecules and a transducer surface,
 843 causing changes in electrical impedance that can be quantified. The impedance response is a
 844 sensitive and selective indicator, allowing for the detection and estimation of PFAS in various
 845 environmental samples. This principle offers a foundation for designing advanced sensing

846 technologies capable of addressing the challenges associated with PFAS monitoring and
847 contributing to ecological safety.

848 Using Au electrodes with o-PD MIPs for impedimetric measurements was more efficient than
849 DPV.¹⁰⁹ With a sensitivity of 0.0001 $\mu\text{g/L}$, Comparatively, the LC-MS/MS technique
850 performed worse than this approach, demonstrating an LOD of 0.041 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for PFOA.
851 Comparably, other researchers detected PFOS with a LOD of 0.00000102 $\mu\text{g/L}$ when Cu
852 electrodes and polyester paper containing poly(aniline) MIPs (PANI) were used.¹¹⁰ According
853 to an additional study, impedance PFAS nano-sensors have significant benefits. They can
854 perform affinity-based capture operations with significant surface areas and pore volumes,
855 improving detection capabilities with an LOD of 0.5 ng/L.¹¹¹

856 The porous structure of MOFs combined with their enormous surface area (10^3 – 10^4 m^2/g)
857 enhances the number of interfaces and active sites suitable for interactions with specific
858 compounds. **Figure 12. A** illustrates the range of contact modalities that MOFs and PFAS
859 species display, including redox, electrostatic, H-bonding, hydrophobic, and attractive
860 intermolecular fluorine–fluorine (F–F) interactions.^{112,113} The PFAS molecule's precise
861 composition and MOF's structural arrangement determine the specific interactions occurring.
862 Specifically, both quantum-chemistry simulations and empirical research show that the
863 negatively charged fluorine functions in individual molecules attract one another. They
864 integrated metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) like Cr-MIL-101 strategically into interdigitated
865 microelectrodes (ID μ Es) to enable rapid detection, shorter reaction times, and the removal of
866 reference electrodes (**Figure 12. B**). Furthermore, by using hydrogen bonds and electrostatic
867 interactions, these nano-sensors show impressive PFAS identification. The small number of
868 publications emphasizes the early stages of this field's study, notwithstanding these
869 developments. More research is needed, especially in verified reference colorimetric
870 techniques, sensitivity, selectivity, and stability enhancements.

871 **Figure 12.** A. Illustrative depiction of the diverse interactions involving fluorinated MOFs and
 872 PFAS molecules, encompassing redox, electrostatic, hydrophobic, hydrogen bonding, and F–
 873 F interactions. Reproduced from Ref.¹¹³. Copyright 2022 John Wiley and Sons. B. Illustration
 874 of the non-planar interdigitated device, showcasing a microchannel formed by a tape-cut and
 875 filled with Cr-MIL101. The microchannel is positioned between the upper and lower
 876 interdigitated microelectrode arrays, providing a top-view perspective (Down - Top view).
 877 Reproduced from Ref.¹¹¹. Copyright 2020 American Chemical Society.

878

879 4.2.5. Electrochemiluminescence PFAS nano-sensors

880 Electrochemical processes and luminescence are combined in electrochemiluminescence
 881 (ECL) photofluorescence-based sensors to produce light.¹¹⁴ These sensors are based on ECL-
 882 based sensing devices, which use high-energy electron processes to make light emissions from
 883 luminophores. These serve as the foundation for the sensitive and targeted detection of
 884 PFAS.¹¹⁵ These nano-sensors' constituent parts usually comprise nano-enhanced catalytic
 885 processes for PFAS breakdown, exposing the possibility of sustainable chemistry in converting
 886 PFAS compounds.¹¹⁶ Furthermore, the advancement and use of innovative nano-sensor
 887 technologies are critical to the identification, tracking, and degradation of PFAS pollutants,
 888 with an emphasis on creative solutions for PFAS contamination at low levels in water sources.
 889 Carbon dots can contribute to the electrochemiluminescence sensing process, opening up new
 890 possibilities for PFAS detection.^{117,118}

891 A novel electrochemiluminescence (ECL) sensor was constructed to detect PFOA. Using
 892 $S_2O_8^{2-}$ as a co-reactant, this sensor used 2D ultrathin g- C_3N_4 (utg- C_3N_4) nanosheets modified
 893 via molecular imprinting polypyrrole as a cathodic ECL emitter (**Figure 13**).¹¹⁹ The utg- C_3N_4
 894 nanosheets functionalized with MIP (MIP@utg- C_3N_4) exhibited a consistent and notable
 895 enhancement of the ECL signal. The ECL signal decreased due to the effective oxidation of

896 PFOA targets by electro-generated strong oxidants, namely $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ radicals produced by
 897 reducing the co-reactant $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$. A lower yield of excited $\text{utg-C}_3\text{N}_4$ ($\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4^*$) was the cause of
 898 this. This novel approach led to the developing of a highly selective and sensitive MIP@utg-
 899 C_3N_4 -based signal-off ECL sensor for PFOA detection. Over PFOA concentrations, the newly
 900 developed ECL sensor demonstrated a linear response in two different ranges: 0.02 to 40.0 ng
 901 mL^{-1} and 50.0–400.0 ng mL^{-1} . The estimated detection limit ($S/N = 3$) was 0.01 ng mL^{-1} (i.e.,
 902 0.01 ppb), which is noteworthy since it shows comparability to results from well-established
 903 LC-MS/MS techniques. However, electrochemiluminescence PFAS nano-sensors are still in
 904 the early stage of research. There is a need for further exploration and optimization for practical
 905 applications. **Table 5** shows a brief comparison of various electrochemical PFAS nano-sensors.

906

907 **Figure 13.** Illustrative electrochemiluminescence detection technique for PFOA with MIP
 908 functionalized $\text{utg-C}_3\text{N}_4$ in $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ system. Reproduced from Ref.¹¹⁹. Copyright 2015 Elsevier.

909 **Table 4.** The attributes of the reported electrochemical (EC) PFAS nano-sensors.

EC Sensor Types	Platform Nanomaterial	Receptor/Probe	Target analyte	Mechanism/PFAS interaction	Range (µg/L)	LOD (µg/L)	Ref.
Voltammetry	Pt nanoelectrodes	Hydrogen gas	PFOA, PFOS	Hydrogen evolution reaction	10-10 ⁴	30 (PFOA); 80 (PFOS)	¹²⁰
	Au NPs	MIP of Polydopamine	PFOS	-	0.01-8	0.0042	¹²¹
	B,N-co-doped carbon nanowalls	MIP of Poly(o-phenylenediamine)	PFOS	Carbon nanostructures create a distinctive arrangement of binding sites within MIPs, exhibiting a strong attraction to PFOS.	1 × 10 ⁻⁵ - 5 × 10 ⁻²	1.2	¹²²
Potentiometry	Glassy carbon macro electrodes (radius 0.0015 m)	A thin layer (75 nm) of o-PD MIP	PFOS	When o-PD was anodically deposited in PFOS presence, it successfully prevented any heterogeneous electron transfer from occurring at the electrode and created MIPs.	0–0.25	0.25	¹⁰²
Photo-electrochemical	AgI nanoparticles–BiOI nanoflake arrays	MIPs of acrylamide	PFOA	The addition of PFOA results in a signal-off indirect photo-electrochemical process by increasing steric hindrance e ⁻ transfer, and decreasing photocurrent.	0.020–1000	0.1	¹⁰⁶

	TiO ₂ nanotube arrays	MIPs of polyacrylamide	PFOS	Increasing the concentration of PFOS proportionately increases photocurrent	250.06–50012.60	86	¹²³
	Screen printed carbon electrodes modified with BiOI nanoflake arrays	MIPs of polyacrylamide	PFOSF	Adding PFOA results in a signal-off indirect photo-electrochemical process by increasing steric hindrance e ⁻ transfer and decreasing photocurrent.	0.05–500.00	0.01	¹²⁴
Impedance	Interdigitated microelectrodes microfluidic probe	MOF Cr-MIL-101	PFOA	The unique shape of the MOF facilitates the convective transport of PFOS, leading to shorter diffusion times and the elimination of capacitance by the double layer.	-	0.005	¹¹¹
	B,N-co-doped carbon nanowalls	MIP of Poly(o-phenylenediamine)	PFOS	Carbon nanostructures produce a unique array of binding sites within MIPs, demonstrating a pronounced affinity for PFOS.	$1 \times 10^{-5} - 5 \times 10^{-2}$	1.2	¹²²
Electrochemiluminescence	ultrathin g-C ₃ N ₄ nanosheets	MIPs of polypyrrole	PFOA	C-F bonding occurs, with a typical peak of F 1s at 688.8 eV & electrochemiluminescence signal "off."	50–400	20	¹¹⁹

910

911

912 **Table 5.** The comparison of various electrochemical PFAS nano-sensors.

Electrochemical PFAS nano-sensors types	Detection Principle	Sensitivity	Specificity	Real-time Monitoring	Advantages	Disadvantages
Voltammetric	Electrochemical redox reactions	High	Moderate	Limited	High sensitivity, simple operation	Limited specificity may require complex electrodes
Potentiometric	Potential difference measurement	Moderate	High	Limited	High specificity, stable signal	Slower response compared to some techniques
Photo-electrochemical	Light-induced redox reactions	Moderate to High	High	Limited	Selective and sensitive, potential for miniaturization	Complex instrumentation, sensitivity to light conditions
Impedance	Measurement of electrical impedance	Moderate to High	Moderate to High	Possible	Label-free, potential for real-time monitoring	Limited feature prominence at higher frequencies
Electrochemiluminescence	Electrochemical process producing light	High	High	Possible	High sensitivity, low detection limits	Instrumentation complexity, limited to specific PFAS

913

914 4.3. Aptamer-based PFAS nano-sensors

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915 Aptamer-based PFAS nano-sensors provide a very sensitive and selective method for detecting
916 PFAS. These nano-sensors take advantage of the unique capabilities of aptamers, single-
917 stranded DNA, or RNA that can attach to particular molecules of interest^{125,126}. The basic idea
918 is to create aptamers with a selectivity for PFAS, allowing the development of nanoscale
919 sensors capable of detecting and measuring these pollutants in water and other environmental
920 samples.¹²⁷ SELEX, which stands for sequential evolution of ligands by exponential
921 enrichment, is a technique that selects aptamers with affinity for a specific target from a huge
922 oligonucleotide library. The SELEX procedure generates 10^6 aptamer sequences. At Base Pair,
923 identifying the top candidates is a sophisticated procedure employing various analytical tools.
924 The engineered aptamer can interact with the target with different binding mechanisms such as
925 induced fit, structural compatibility, electrostatic interaction, and hydrogen bridges (**Figure 14.**
926 **A**).¹²⁸

927 Environmental sensing has moved forward significantly since pioneered the use of DNA
928 aptamers to detect PFAS and related fluorinated chemicals.¹²⁹ With its unique binding affinity
929 to PFOA, the designed aptamer was easily integrated into a fluorescence-based aptamer sensor,
930 allowing for sensing aqueous PFOA at a remarkable LOD of 0.17 μM . The aptamer's
931 conformational shift upon interaction with PFOA mitigated the quenching impact of
932 fluorescein fluorescence, which was the basis for the sensing mechanism. Structural insights
933 are displayed in **Figure 14. B** indicated the expected configuration of the 30-base aptamer after
934 PFOA binding. The aptamer was combined with PFOA solutions at varying concentrations
935 (0.5–50 μM) for the experimental evaluations. The fluorescence intensity was measured after
936 40 minutes of incubation, showing a linear increase with increasing PFOA concentrations.

937 Using 1D-1H and 2D NOESY NMR methods, the secondary structure of the PFOA_JYP_2
938 aptamer was investigated both with and without PFOA (**Figure 14. B**).¹²⁹ Chemical shift
939 changes in the 10–14 ppm range were seen in 1D-1H NMR spectra, corresponding to the imino
940 protons of the guanine (G) and thymine (T) bases.¹³⁰ In the absence of PFOA, the aptamer
941 displayed two peaks at 13.4 and 13.5 ppm and five peaks at 12.4, 12.44, 12.5, 12.6, and 12.8
942 ppm, signifying two thymines and five guanines, respectively, within the Watson-Crick base
943 pairing range (12–14 ppm). New peaks at 12.1, 12.2, 12.7, and 13.6 ppm appeared in the
944 presence of PFOA, indicating three guanines and one thymine. Furthermore, peaks (e.g., 10.5,
945 10.8, 11.3, 11.5, and 11.8 ppm) that correspond to non-Watson-Crick base guanines and

946 thymines have emerged in the 10–12 ppm range. According to Neves and colleagues, the
 947 appearance of these base pairs indicated conformational alterations and aptamer folding
 948 brought on by PFOA contact.¹³¹

949 Significantly, the sensor demonstrated very little sensitivity to interferences, as demonstrated
 950 by its effective use in wastewater discharge monitoring.¹²⁹ The aptamer sensor based on
 951 fluorescence exhibited exceptional sensitivity, making it especially appropriate for detecting
 952 levels of PFOA in water close to unintentional spills and manufacturing regions where elevated
 953 amounts of PFAS are predictable. Although the present LOD cannot measure concentrations
 954 below regulatory limits, fluorescence-based sensors have an advantage in that they can function
 955 in solution without requiring immobilization of the receptor on solid supports. So far, this is
 956 the sole report of PFAS detection using aptamers.

957 **Figure 14.** A. Schematic representation of structure and mechanisms of aptamer target
 958 complex formation. Reproduced from Ref. ¹²⁸. Copyright 2013 Swiss Med Wkly. B.
 959 PFOA_JYP_2 predicted 2D structures with 0 mM PFOA & 0.5 mM PFOA and 1D-¹H NMR
 960 spectra showing the changes in Watson-Crick pairing and non-canonical pairing before and
 961 after adding & 0.5 mM PFO. Reproduced from Ref. ¹²⁹. Copyright 2022 Elsevier.

962

963 4.4. Immunonanosenors for PFAS

964 Immunonanosensors for PFAS detection using particular antibodies or antigens, has been
965 reported to gather and determine PFAS molecules. These nano-sensors exploit antibodies'
966 extremely specific binding interactions with PFAS chemicals, enabling sensitive and accurate
967 detection. The immobilization of these identification components on nanomaterials increases
968 the sensor's surface area, allowing for greater binding capacity and enhancing overall PFAS
969 detection performance.¹³²

970 Monoclonal and custom-designed antibodies, often created through a surrogate for
971 amplification, were employed to achieve precise and selective binding of PFA compounds.¹³³
972 Utilizing monoclonal antibodies targeting α -lipoic acid compounds, self-assembled
973 monolayers of these antibodies were affixed onto the surface of plastic optical fibers (POF) by
974 Cennamo and colleagues (**Figure 15. A**).¹³⁴ This immunonanosensor has shown an LOD of
975 0.21 $\mu\text{g/L}$ for both PFOS and PFOA. These sensors formed self-assembling monolayers on
976 plastic optical fiber surfaces by grafting antibodies created using an enzyme-linked
977 immunosorbent assay (ELISA) onto AuNPs functionalized with α -lipophilic acid molecules.
978 SPR was used for signal detection, and MIPs were attached to AuNPs to act as a sensing
979 platform. The recognition event, governed by anionic functional groups of PFAS and van der
980 Waals interactions, induced measurable signals and resonant wavelength shifts upon contact
981 with PFOS/PFOA, reflecting changes in refractive index.¹³⁵

982 As an agonist for peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha (PPAR), PFAS has
983 ramifications for activating several target genes via this transcription factor. A new
984 immunonanosensor captures the active PPAR complex using monoclonal anti-PPAR
985 antibodies on a microplate.¹³⁶ In this system, AuNPs, modified with PPAR α -responsive
986 elements (PPRE), selectively bind to the activated complex, and silver is introduced to amplify
987 the signal, exhibiting a positive correlation with PFOS concentration and achieving a low
988 detection limit of 5 ppt (**Figure 15 B**). Another sensor employs streptavidin-modified quantum
989 dots (QDs) as a fluorescent marker that binds to the PFOS-activated PPAR α complex.¹³⁷ PFOS
990 concentration is directly correlated with the QDs' fluorescence intensity, with a 2.5 ppt low
991 detection limit. Although PPAR α sensors are promising, their field adaptability is limited due
992 to the repeated reagent additions, washing, and incubation processes they currently need. This

993 approach's application might be increased by converting it to a lateral flow assay format,
 994 allowing for on-site determination of total PFAS concentration.

995
 996 **Figure 15.** A. Schematics of Optical immunosensor surface functionalized with gold - system
 997 based on POF-SPR platform. Reproduced from Ref. ¹³⁴. Copyright 2018 Elsevier. B
 998 Schematics of PFOS Detection based on the interaction between PPRE-modified gold
 999 nanoparticle probes and activated PPAR α with silver. Reproduced from Ref. ¹³⁶. Copyright
 1000 2011 Elsevier. C. Illustrations of an electrochemical immunosensor are presented for the highly
 1001 sensitive detection of PFOS. The sensor utilizes glassy carbon electrodes (GCE) modified with
 1002 multi-walled carbon nanohorns (MWNHs) as substrates for both bioanode and biocathode.
 1003 Biocatalysts, namely glutamic dehydrogenase (GLDH) and bilirubin oxidase (BOD), are
 1004 employed in the detection process. Reproduced from Ref. ¹³⁸. Copyright 2014 The
 1005 Electrochemical Society of Japan.

1006
 1007 Using modified glassy carbon electrodes (GCE) as the bioanode and biocathode substrates,
 1008 glutamic dehydrogenase (GLDH) and bilirubin oxidase (BOD) as biocatalysts, an innovative
 1009 electrochemical immunosensor was developed for the sensitive detection of PFOS (**Figure 15.**
 1010 **C**).¹³⁸ The immunosensor takes use of PFOS's inhibitory effect on biocatalysis within an

1011 enzymatic biofuel cell (BFC). The one-compartment BFC has an open circuit potential (V_{oc})
 1012 of 30.65 mV and a maximum power density of 27.5 W/cm². The biosensor displayed a broad
 1013 linear detection range of 5 to 500 nmol/L based on V_{oc} and PFOS concentrations. It also
 1014 demonstrated a significant correlation ($R^2 = 0.976$) with a measurement frequency of three
 1015 times ($n = 3$). The PFOS may further lower the BFC's open circuit voltage by blocking the
 1016 enzymatic activity of bilirubin oxidase and glutamic dehydrogenase. Following a 20-minute
 1017 interaction, 1.6 nmol/L was the detection limit. Furthermore, in micro-polluted water, the
 1018 biosensor demonstrated significant selectivity for PFOS over structurally related perfluorinated
 1019 compounds and contemporaneous molecules (SMNBS and SDS). For PFOS detection in
 1020 complex aqueous matrices using the standard addition technique, precision was confirmed with
 1021 an RSD ranging from 3.6% to 7.7%. For a broader overview of the nano-sensors for PFAS
 1022 detection the reader can refer to **Table 6**.

1023 **Table 6. Comparison of the nano-sensors for PFAS detection.**

Type of Sensor	LOD (ng/L)	LOQ (ng/L)	Sensitivity	Major Advantages	Major Disadvantages
Optical Sensors	0.1–10	0.5–50	High; dependent on fluorophore or chromophore properties	High specificity and rapid detection; suitable for real-time monitoring; non-invasive methods	High cost of instrumentation; may require complex sample preparation for environmental matrices
Electrochemical Sensors	1–100	5–200	High; depends on electrode material and surface modifications	Simple instrumentation; portable and cost-effective; amenable to on-site applications	May suffer from electrode fouling; requires precise calibration for environmental samples
Aptamer-Based Sensors	0.01–1	0.05–5	Very high; aptamers offer strong binding affinity and specificity	Highly specific recognition of PFAS; tunable for different PFAS compounds; reusable in certain formats	Production of aptamers can be costly and time-consuming; stability may be limited under environmental conditions
Immunosensors	0.1–5	0.5–20	High; depends on antibody-	High specificity; adaptable to	Expensive antibodies; limited

			antigen interactions	multiple formats (e.g., ELISA, lateral flow assays); well-established methods	reusability: potential for cross-reactivity among structurally similar PFAS
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1024 *LOD** – Limit of detection, *LOQ*** – Limit of quantification

1025 5. Possible mechanism of interaction of PFAS with nano-probes

1026 Implementation of different materials has been challenging for sensing or removal of PFAS
 1027 because the water stream to be decontaminated contains organic molecules $2.5 \pm 0.3 \times 10^6$
 1028 times higher than the PFAS, and the remediation of the water source will lead to a concentration
 1029 of the non-fluorinated organic molecules, whereas the majority of the PFAS still present in the
 1030 water bodies.³² Polluted groundwater stream also has the presence of different particles (micro
 1031 to nano dimensional) and salts dissolved in it. Solution phase sorption of PFAS depends on the
 1032 net free energy change accompanying the interactional transition of PFAS molecules from the
 1033 aqueous phase to the solid phase. This can be a combination of both (i) solvation effects like
 1034 enthalpy and entropy changes associated with solvent-solvent, solute-solvent, and solvent-
 1035 sorbent interaction and (ii) molecular interactions between solute and sorbent. Thus, in this
 1036 segment, we highlight different chemical interactions as possible sources for the selective
 1037 sensing and removal of PFAS from the water bodies. **Figure 16** summarises all the possible
 1038 interactions of PFAS moiety with nano-probes.

1039 5.1. Fluorophilic interactions

1040 Non-bonding interactions are decisive in recognizing two or more molecular entities, which is
 1041 crucial for sensing inert entities like the PFAS. The C-F bonds may participate in dipole-dipole
 1042 and point dipole interaction with ionic groups and dipolar groups, which can lead to
 1043 intermolecular dispersion interactions C-F...F-C, often referred to as fluorophilic
 1044 interactions.¹³⁹ This fluorophilic interaction is weak, but the magnitude depends on the number
 1045 of interacting groups (**Figure 16. A**). This proposition can be easily supported by literature
 1046 reports where ionic fluorogels and magnetic fluorinated polymers were employed for PFAS
 1047 removal from water sources, which showed high affinity and high capacity of PFAS removal
 1048 from water bodies compared to non-fluorinated versions of the sorbents.^{23,140} The removal
 1049 efficiencies drastically decreased due to downsizing the chain length of the PFAS, resulting in

1050 a decrease in the fluorinated polymer's sorption properties. Thus, in sensing small, chained
1051 PFAS molecules the electrostatic interaction may play a governing role over fluorophilic
1052 interactions.¹⁴¹

1053 5.2. Electrostatic interactions

1054 Electrostatic interaction is a form of non-covalent interaction between charged particles that
1055 can be attractive as well as repulsive. There are two sources of electrostatic interaction in PFAS,
1056 the first being the low pK_a of PFAS in an aqueous solution.¹⁴² Owing to the electron-
1057 withdrawing effect of the fluoroalkyl chains, the head group containing CO_2 and SO_3 is always
1058 in its ionic form (**Figure 16. B**). The long chain PFAS are the most common in the aquatic
1059 environment. With concentrations above 1000 ppm, they can form micelles or hemimicelles in
1060 groundwater, attaining stability in the aquatic environment. PFAS can also aggregate with
1061 foreign particles suspended in water bodies to form aggregation even at concentrations lower
1062 than the CMC. PFAS are generally found as anions, but depending on the pH and functional
1063 groups present, they can be anionic, cationic, and Zwitterionic.¹⁴³ In the case of anionic PFAS,
1064 when the solution pH is below the pK_a , it exists as a neutral molecule, whereas it is above the
1065 pK_a value as the anion. It is the opposite for the case of cationic PFAS where at lower pH values
1066 than pK_a it exists in the cationic form; otherwise, in the neutral form. But for zwitterionic PFAS,
1067 when the solution pH is lower than the first pK_a , it exists as a cation and is higher than the
1068 second pK_a as anions. When the pH of the solution is between these two limiting values, it
1069 exists as charge neutralized species with separated cationic and anionic functionalities. The
1070 cationic and Zwitterionic PFAS sensing possess a strong dependency on the pH of the solution.
1071 This affects its transportation and adsorption, posing severe difficulties in the design of
1072 materials for the remediation of these species. Banking on electrostatic interactions and
1073 hydrophobic interactions, PFAS uptake can be accomplished from water sources by ion
1074 exchangers.

1075 5.3. Ion exchange

1076 The ion exchange resin attracts molecules of opposite charge and releases an equal number of
1077 the same charged ions to the aqueous solution until an equilibrium is established.¹¹² The
1078 effectiveness of this process depends on different factors - the charge on the PFAS ion, the
1079 charge density of the PFAS ions, the polarizability of the ions, the degree of cross-linking of
1080 the ion exchange resin, the ion exchange capacity of the resin, functional groups present in the
1081 ion exchanger, nature and concentration of the eluted ions.⁴³ The most crucial factor of all is

1082 the resin's ion exchange capacity, which varies with the pH of the solution and may affect the
1083 uptake of PFAS with an increase in pH (**Figure 16. C**). Also, the coexistence of other anions
1084 in the solution may compete with the uptake of PFAS, making the presence of hydrophobic
1085 interaction a governing factor in the PFAS uptake.¹⁴⁴

1086 **5.4. Hydrophobic interaction**

1087 Structurally, PFAS comprises a hydrophobic tail predominantly due to the C-F bonds and a
1088 hydrophilic head comprising the sulphonic acid and carboxylic acid head groups. This type of
1089 interaction describes the strong interaction between a hydrophobic molecule and a hydrophobic
1090 carbon surface.¹⁴⁵ One of the cheapest and benchmark materials for PFAS sensing is activated
1091 carbon, which is already used for remediation and filtering applications.¹⁴⁶ Electrostatic and
1092 non-electrostatic interactions head the adsorption of molecules like PFAS over activated
1093 carbon. For non-electrostatic, it is the dispersion and hydrophobic interaction, whereas the
1094 electrostatic or columbic interaction applies for PFAS in dissociated form in aqueous condition.
1095 Adsorption of PFAS over activated carbon is a result of their surface composition and
1096 heteroatom content, mainly the surface oxygen content. When a material like activated carbon,
1097 carbon dots, or graphene is immersed in an aqueous solution, it either attains ionic form by
1098 dissociating the surface functionalities present or absorbs the ion in the solution to develop a
1099 surface charge.¹⁴⁷ The negative surface charge originates from the dissociation of surface
1100 functionalities like carboxylates, sulphonates, or phenolic groups. The positively charged
1101 character of the surface originates from the adsorption of positively charged metal ions on the
1102 surface and due to electron densities, which act as Lewis base abstracting protons from the
1103 solution. Thus, the development of surface charge by carbon materials enhances the
1104 possibilities of electrostatic interaction with the PAFS, leading to adsorption. The surface
1105 oxygen content also dictates the hydrophobic interaction between the hydrophobic PFAS
1106 molecule and the hydrophobic carbon surface.¹⁴⁸ Water molecules in the aqueous solution have
1107 a strong tendency to associate with each other to retain their structure, thus phasing out the
1108 hydrophobic components to form a separate phase (**Figure 16. D**). Therefore, hydrophobic
1109 interaction is advantageous for sensing and remediation of long-chain PFAS molecules in
1110 aqueous environment.

1111 **5.5. Cation Bridge Interaction**

1112 PFAS molecules, including long-chain PFSA and short-chain PFCA, showed enhanced
1113 sorption in the presence of divalent cationic species.¹⁴⁹ This was not only due to the pH of the

1114 solution but also an effect of ionic strength in charge neutralization of anionic PFAS. Finally,
1115 the formation of cationic bridges between the -ve-charged head group of PFAS molecules and
1116 the -ve-charged surface of the absorber is under investigation. The effect is small for the short-
1117 chain PFAS but stronger for the long-chain PFAS and becomes a predominant factor with an
1118 increase in the charge density of the cation in the solution. This phenomenon has excellent
1119 benefits when polyvalent cations are used, which helps better pack PFAS molecules on the
1120 adsorbent surfaces.¹⁵⁰ Generally, the adsorption of PFAS on surfaces decreases with the
1121 increase in pH. Still, an opposite trend was observed due to the presence of divalent cations in
1122 the solution as the alkalinity of the solution increases the -ve charge density of the absorbent
1123 surface, improving the cation bridge interaction (**Figure 16. E**). Apart from this, the divalent
1124 cation can also bridge two PFAS anions in the solution. Single-atom functionalized graphene
1125 and carbon dots can be very effective in PFAS remediation as the transition metal single atoms
1126 are supported or stabilized by primary, secondary, or tertiary amine-based donors or
1127 carboxylate functionalities and can favourably interact with the anionic PFAS via salt bridge
1128 interaction, leading counterion ion condensation and phase separation.

1129 **5.6. Hydrogen bonding**

1130 The fluorocarbon tail of the PFAS does not participate in H-bonding interaction due to high
1131 stabilization of the s and p orbitals, making the F groups nonpolarizable and a poor acceptor of
1132 hydrogen bonds, but the oxygen atoms present in the head functional groups are suitable
1133 acceptors of Hydrogen bonding (**Figure 16. F**). PFAS shows weak intermolecular interaction
1134 with the surrounding phase, which is the leading cause of its mobility and persistent air
1135 pollution unless strong forces like hydrogen bonding interaction between the head group and
1136 the water molecules hold them together.¹⁴³ The PFAS molecules in the ionized form at the air-
1137 water interface interact to form a belt of hydrogen bonding interactions.¹⁵¹ This interaction may
1138 help PFAS in foam stabilization and decrease its mobility. pH influences the extent of H-
1139 bonding of the PFAS at the Air-Water interface, where the pK_a of PFAS at the surface and bulk
1140 are different leading to the formation of dissimilar aggregation states.¹⁵² Aggregation can also
1141 be caused due to contributions from van der Waals interaction.

1142 **5.7. van der Waals interaction**

1143 Weak intermolecular interaction is the leading cause of micellization or aggregation of
1144 PFAS.¹⁵³ In the long interaction range, the particles tend to attract each other due to van der
1145 Waals forces, and by the contribution of other interacting forces like electrostatic interaction,

1146 they come close to each other, whereas the van der Waals forces tend to repel each other. This
 1147 particle-particle interaction with respect to separation distance causes stabilization of colloidal
 1148 PFAS solutions (**Figure 16. G**). It can be essential in sensing and separating PFAS in aqueous
 1149 solution.

1150 5.8. π - π interaction

1151 In the case of the PFAS having phenyl aromatic rings as substituents, they have a crucial
 1152 driving force in the form of π - π interaction to get absorbed on the surface of the absorber and
 1153 have a π -electron cloud (**Figure 16. H**). Here, one of the systems acts as an electron-rich moiety
 1154 containing π -electron cloud acts as a donor, interacting with entities that have electron deficient
 1155 π -electron systems, leading to donor-acceptor π - π interaction.¹⁵⁴

1156

1157 **Figure 16.** Representation of different types of molecular level interaction pertaining to sensing
 1158 and remediation of PFAS molecules in aqueous solutions. **A.** Fluorophilic interaction (dashed
 1159 lines) occurring between a fluorinated carbon substrate and PFOS. **B.** Electrostatic interaction
 1160 occurring between quaternary ammonium cation and the PFOS anion. **C.** The ammonium

1161 cations are part of an anion exchange resin where the PFOS anion faces strong electrostatic
1162 interaction to separate from the aqueous elution phase. **D.** Water present in the systems attains
1163 its stable structure by phasing out the carbon material to participate in hydrophobic interaction
1164 with the carbon chain of PFOS. **E.** Carboxylate-derived carbon support participating in sensing
1165 of PFOS anions via Ca^{2+} cation bridge interaction. **F.** The carboxylic acid groups of the
1166 substrate and the PFAS interact via hydrogen bonding interactions. **G.** van der Waals
1167 interaction stabilizes solution-phase self-assembly of PFOS in aqueous solution **H.** π - π
1168 interaction leading to adsorption of the phenyl substituted PFAS over carbon material having
1169 π -delocalized system

1170
1171 Banking on the aforementioned molecular level interactions, metal single-atom supported
1172 graphene and carbon dots (CDs) can be a viable substrate for sensing PFAS.^{61,155,156} To support
1173 our proposition, we now highlight the role of graphene and carbon dots substrates in sensing
1174 applications. CDs, by virtue, showcase excellent optical properties with strong absorption and
1175 emission properties with high photostability. CDs were implemented for sensing Hg^{2+} for tap
1176 water and mineral water. The surface functionalities like carboxyl and ammine groups led to
1177 enhanced optical sensing of Hg^{2+} with a sensitivity in ppb limit. The strong metal-CD support
1178 interaction not only perturbed the photoexcited state of the CDs but also decreased the lifetime
1179 of the Hg^{2+} -CD photoexcited state, which kept on decreasing with the increase in the
1180 concentration of the Hg^{2+} in the solution.¹⁵⁷ Thus, metal single-atom functionalized CDs can
1181 be a viable substrate for optical sensing of PFAS owing to strong electrostatic interaction
1182 between the positively charged single metal atom and negatively charged PFAS molecules,
1183 hydrophobic and strong van der Waals interaction between the CDs substrate and the PFAS
1184 molecules. Different extents of interaction with different first-row transition metal atoms may
1185 also lead to selective lifetime-based sensing of PFAS. On the other hand, functionalized
1186 graphene and its quantum dots interface have been well studied in substitution of different
1187 functionalities, which has strong interaction with metal ions leading to the formation of single
1188 atom graphene materials.^{158,159} By virtue of high electron mobility facilitated by graphene,
1189 selectivity of intermolecular interactions imparted by the surface functionalities and redox
1190 properties by transition metal single atoms it becomes an excellent candidate for
1191 electrochemical sensing of PFAS.¹⁶⁰ Substrates like Fluorographene may lead to enhanced
1192 fluorophilic interaction, carbon framework in hydrophobic interaction, and the single metal
1193 sites in electrostatic interaction may lead to enhanced selectivity of PFAS sensing over the
1194 hydrocarbons present in water bodies.¹⁴⁷ The added benefit of graphene-based systems is that
1195 they can participate in π - π interaction with the PFAS, leading to selective detection of PFAS
1196 with phenyl substituents over the saturated carbon-chained PFAS.

1197 **6. Techniques for PFAS removal and integration with electrochemical methods using** 1198 **nanomaterials**

1199 PFAS removal is a crucial task because of its chemical stability, persistence, and extensive
1200 environmental presence. Adsorption, advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), membrane
1201 filtering, and biological approaches are all common methods for PFAS removal, each having
1202 its own level of efficiency and limitations. Recent advances in nanomaterials have considerably
1203 improved the effectiveness of these treatments, particularly when combined with
1204 electrochemical methods, allowing for more inventive and economical PFAS remediation.

1205 **6.1. Adsorption**

1206 Nanomaterials like carbon nanotubes, graphene oxide, MOFs, and functionalized silica have
1207 high surface areas, tunable porosity, and functional surface groups, making them effective
1208 PFAS adsorbents.^{161,162} For example, carbon dots functionalized with amines or quaternary
1209 ammonium groups interact strongly with PFAS via electrostatic and hydrophobic forces.
1210 Integrating these nanoparticles into adsorption columns or filters can result in excellent PFAS
1211 removal effectiveness, even at low concentrations.

1212 **6.2. Advanced Oxidation Processes**

1213 Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) employ nanomaterials such as TiO₂ and doped ZnO
1214 nanoparticles to destroy PFAS using photocatalytic processes.¹⁶³ When triggered by UV or
1215 visible light, these nanoparticles produce reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can degrade
1216 PFAS into shorter-chain chemicals or mineralize them entirely. Doping TiO₂ with fluorine or
1217 nitrogen can enhance light absorption to the visible spectrum, leading to higher efficiency in
1218 real-world situations.

1219 **6.3. Membrane Filtration**

1220 Nanomaterial-enabled membranes, including graphene oxide-coated or nanofiber membranes,
1221 improve classic filtering methods like reverse osmosis (RO) and nanofiltration (NF).^{164,165}
1222 These membranes' exact pore diameters and chemical selectivity allow them to successfully
1223 reject PFAS compounds. Furthermore, they have antifouling qualities that increase operating
1224 longevity.

1225 **6.4. Biological Methods**

1226 Nanomaterials can promote microbial systems by functioning as electron carriers or catalytic
1227 sites, notwithstanding PFAS's resistance to biodegradation.¹⁶⁶ Biochar and carbon nanotubes,
1228 for example, can aid in the breakdown of PFAS precursors by facilitating electron transfer
1229 during microbial degradation processes.

1230 **6.5. Integration of Electrochemical Techniques with Nanomaterial-Based Approaches**

1231 Electrochemical approaches, such as electrochemical oxidation, reduction, and
1232 electrocatalysis, provide potential avenues for PFAS degradation.¹⁶⁷ These approaches can be
1233 successfully combined with nanomaterial-based PFAS removal strategies to solve their
1234 individual limitations and improve performance:

1235 **6.5.1. Electrochemical Oxidation Coupled with Adsorption**

1236 Nanomaterials like carbon nanotubes and MOFs can absorb and concentrate PFAS in water by
1237 electrochemical oxidation and adsorption. Electrochemical oxidation can then be employed to
1238 destroy the adsorbed PFAS on the adsorbent, renewing the nanomaterial for future usage. For
1239 example, when paired with carbon-based adsorbents, boron-doped diamond (BDD) electrodes
1240 may effectively oxidize PFAS, resulting in near-complete mineralization of pollutants.

1241 **6.5.2. Electro-Fenton Processes with Nanomaterials**

1242 Electro-Fenton processes, which produce hydroxyl radicals through electrochemical reactions,
1243 can be enhanced using nanocatalysts such as iron oxide nanoparticles. These nanoparticles
1244 serve as either homogeneous or heterogeneous catalysts, boosting ROS generation and
1245 increasing PFAS breakdown rates. Magnetic nanoparticles, for example, make it easier to
1246 recover and reuse materials, hence boosting process sustainability.

1247 **6.5.3. Electrochemical Membrane Reactors**

1248 Nanomaterial-coated membranes, including graphene oxide and carbon nanotubes, can
1249 function as electrochemical reactors. Using an electric potential, these membranes can destroy
1250 PFAS molecules while also purifying water. This dual functionality lowers energy usage and
1251 operational complexity.

1252 In conclusion, combining electrochemical techniques with nanomaterial-based PFAS removal
1253 technologies provides a very effective and long-term solution to the issues faced by PFAS
1254 contamination. Nanomaterials such as carbon-based adsorbents, catalytic nanoparticles, and
1255 improved membranes improve the effectiveness of adsorption, AOPs, and filtering processes,

1256 while electrochemical approaches provide effective routes for PFAS degradation and material
1257 regeneration. By harnessing the synergies between these technologies, it is feasible to obtain
1258 better removal rates, lower energy usage, and less secondary waste. Continued study and
1259 development of these integrated systems will be essential for developing scalable and cost-
1260 effective PFAS remediation methods.

1261 **7. Challenges, prospects, and conclusion**

1262 Due to these pollutants' ubiquitous and persistent character, accurate sensing of per- and PFAS
1263 is critical for successful environmental monitoring. PFAS are found in diverse matrices,
1264 including water, soil, and air, and pose a substantial hazard to ecosystems and human health.
1265 Sensing technologies are critical in measuring PFAS concentrations in such samples, giving
1266 necessary data for risk assessment and informed decision-making. Real-time and accurate
1267 detection tools, such as sensors created particularly for PFAS, provide significant information
1268 on contamination. A dependable PFAS sensor can provide near-instant data capturing to allow
1269 rapid actions to limit exposure hazards. Furthermore, critical levels of data for water quality
1270 managers, government agencies, and communities for implementing targeted remediation
1271 plans and ensuring regulatory compliance.

1272 The sensing of PFAS poses considerable hurdles for sensors due to their complex and
1273 diversified nature. Given that PFAS have diverse compositions and structures, a single
1274 interaction type is insufficient for a thorough detection. Sophisticated methods that incorporate
1275 several identification components are required to provide PFAS sensing that is precise and
1276 dependable. These components should be able to distinguish between the distinct qualities of
1277 different PFAS kinds simultaneously. Overcoming PFAS variety and chemistry complexities
1278 is crucial for sensor development, creating a robust and adaptive platform that can handle the
1279 peculiarities of diverse PFAS compounds. Given the complex chemical differences across the
1280 PFAS family, researchers continuously investigate novel approaches to improve sensor
1281 selectivity and sensitivity.

1282 The choice between specific and broad-spectrum PFAS detection sensors is a critical factor in
1283 addressing the complexities of PFAS contamination. Sensors tailored to individual PFAS
1284 compounds, such as PFOS or PFOA, offer high specificity but may fall short of capturing the
1285 full spectrum of PFAS diversity. On the other hand, sensors designed to detect PFCAs, PFSA, or
1286 total PFAS provide a broader perspective, ensuring a comprehensive approach to
1287 monitoring. Striking the right balance between specificity and broad applicability is paramount,

1288 considering the varied prevalence of PFAS in different environments. Achieving this balance
1289 enables effective monitoring that caters to the specific chemical makeup of PFAS contaminants
1290 while accommodating the diverse monitoring needs dictated by their widespread occurrence in
1291 various settings.

1292 A combination of environmental parameters, nanomaterial characteristics, and interactions at
1293 the solute-sensing interface creates significant challenges in creating PFAS nano-sensors.
1294 Ecological aspects like temperature, moisture, and pH levels substantially influence nano-
1295 sensors' functioning. Maintaining sensor stability in various environments necessitates novel
1296 approaches, such as strong coatings or encapsulating methods to protect nanomaterials from
1297 external impacts. Nanomaterial parameters, such as size, composition, and surface features,
1298 substantially influence sensor sensitivity and selectivity. Ensuring the best performance of
1299 nano-sensors necessitates a thorough understanding of these features to create materials that
1300 improve PFAS detection accuracy. Furthermore, the complex interactions at the solute-sensing
1301 surface highlight the need for surface engineering techniques that increase selective and
1302 reliable PFAS binding. Given the dynamic nature of environmental matrices, flexible sensor
1303 designs capable of handling various situations are required. Addressing these issues will be
1304 imperative in improving the reliability and effectiveness of PFAS nano-sensors, opening the
1305 path for their successful deployment in environmental monitoring applications.

1306 The vital need for real-time evaluation during soil and wastewater remediation operations is
1307 driving up demand for field-deployable continuous monitoring sensors in the context of PFAS
1308 detection. Continuous monitoring is required by regulatory requirements to guarantee
1309 compliance with permissible PFAS concentrations. This pressing requirement has fueled
1310 research into creating robust sensors capable of withstanding various environmental
1311 conditions. These sensors are critical in measuring PFAS levels in real time, allowing operators
1312 to respond quickly to swings and departures from regulatory norms. These sensors' real-time
1313 data enables proactive decision-making in environmental management, allowing for effective
1314 and timely actions to mitigate PFAS pollution. The development of sensors is consistent with
1315 the overall objective of protecting environmental quality and human health in the face of PFAS
1316 issues.

1317 Technological developments in semiconductor and metallic nanoparticles provide bright
1318 prospects for the PFAS sensing industry. The introduction of electrical, optical, and catalytic
1319 capabilities is the main reason these materials have a revolutionary effect. Because of their

1320 unique qualities—such as increased sensitivity and selectivity—metallic nanoparticles and
1321 semiconductors are excellent choices for enhancing PFAS detection techniques. These cutting-
1322 edge materials may be used in sensor designs to increase their application, especially in
1323 analytical instruments. While optical features improve detection accuracy, electronic qualities
1324 allow for effective signal transduction. Their catalytic functionality is a further factor raising
1325 the PFAS sensors' total sensitivity. With enhanced capabilities for precise and effective PFAS
1326 detection in diverse environmental conditions, this development in sensor technology
1327 represents a substantial advancement. It addresses critical demands in ecological monitoring
1328 and management. Overall, deploying PFAS nano-sensors in environmental monitoring requires
1329 overcoming obstacles, including sensitivity and selectivity problems. Using these nano-
1330 sensors' potentials provides a viable path for accurate and timely detection, greatly aiding in
1331 cleanup operations and expanding our knowledge of the effects of PFAS on ecosystems.

1332

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1340

1341 **Conflict of interest**

1342 There is no conflict of interest among authors.

1343

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- No primary research results, software or code have been included and no new data were generated or analysed as part of this review.

